

SPATIAL

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Abstract	The SPATIAL project aims to achieve one of Europe's top priorities: trustworthy artificial intelligence, with a particular focus on trustworthiness in the cyber security domain. This document is the first version of the SPATIAL project's exploitation plan, based on the cooperation and exchange that took place during the first year of the project, including the project's first deliverables, the initial market assessment, and partner inputs and two workshops. It provides the background and context for the SPATIAL project, a methodology for its development, and outlines the strategy and concrete activities for the exploitation of the project's results.
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Nature of the deliverable:		R*
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PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SPATIAL project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document represents the first version of the exploitation plan for the SPATIAL project: Security and Privacy Accountable Technology Innovations, Algorithms, and Machine Learning. The project aims to address the challenges and uncertainties in AI, specifically in the cybersecurity sector. The European Union Commission recognizes the importance of trustworthy AI and has defined three pillars for it to be lawful, ethical, and robust. However, the opacity of AI algorithms and the lack of transparency in data processing are major concerns for data privacy and security. Therefore, the SPATIAL project aims to contribute to accountability in AI by developing methods for making AI algorithms more transparent and explainable. The project focuses on three key areas: privacy, resilience, and accountability. Privacy refers to the appropriate handling of data, including consent, notice, preservation mechanisms, and regulatory obligations. Resilience refers to the ability of ICT systems to produce the intended outcome continuously despite failures or crises, such as cyber attacks or security breaches. Accountability refers to the legal and ethical obligation of organizations to accept responsibility for their AI solutions and to disclose the results in a transparent manner.

Preliminary exploitation plan is based on the cooperation and exchange that occurred during the first year of the project, the project's first deliverables, the initial market assessment, and, finally, the activities that were conducted in the form of partner inputs and two workshops.

The exploitation plan outlines the SPATIAL background and context, a methodology that is the foundation for the development of this deliverable, drafts the strategy and plans the concrete activities toward the exploitation of the project's outcomes.

For the full understanding of SPATIAL overall objectives and its outcomes, i.e., results that will be exploited it was necessary to describe its general background. In that sense, the report outlines, Artificial Intelligence and Cyber Security technology context, and the application of AI in this particular domain are described with a brief exposition of cyberattacks as the core interest of the SPATIAL project. Artificial Intelligence is recapped from the perspective of its overall benefits as well as the challenges and deficiencies it contains. The European Union's strategic focus on technology leadership, specifically in the area of Artificial Intelligence, and its commitment to protecting core principles and citizens' rights in relation to these technologies, are presented as being essential for the project's success. The project background provided the foundation for understanding the consortium joint Key Exploitable results as well as individual exploitation plans by the project partners articulated in the proposal phase which are also outlined.

After one year of the project duration, collaboration and exchange including the realization of two important deliverables, conditions are created for consolidation and refinement of

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individual exploitation results described in the proposal phase, and additionally mapping their routes and categorization. For that purpose, project partners are provided with an exploitation matrix that is presented for each individual exploitation result. The value proposition workshop is organised as the first in a row of workshops as the core activities for support of the exploitation of results generated in the SPATIAL project. The aim of the value proposition workshop was to formulate a value or benefit that each exploitation result provides. An important difference is emphasised between exploitation results that can be in form of a product, solution, feature, tool, method, or guideline and the specific value it produces for targeted stakeholders, audiences, or customers.

Following the workshop, another was organized for the creation of business models for each partner using a Business Model Canvas. A business model canvas is a single reference model for high-level analysis of nine building blocks that form the foundations of every successful business and in the context of the SPATIAL project foundation for partners' exploitation activities. Partner Mainflux Labs coordinated these workshops involving all consortium partners.

The conclusions of this workshop serve as the foundation for this deliverable; all outcomes and proposed modifications were considered and incorporated into this document.

Following these sections, the initial market assessment and research is provided covering important areas of the global economy, the size of the market potential barriers as well as an overview of companies that are utilizing artificial intelligence for cybersecurity solutions. Utilizing the outcomes of the workshops as well as a SWOT analysis and specific strategic framework, recommendations for the Exploitation strategy are outlined in the concluding part of the market research. The SWOT analysis of the SPATIAL results identified the strengths of these solutions including improved performance, enhanced trust, and market differentiation. However, they also have weaknesses such as overhead costs and fear of change. Opportunities for growth include increased demand and legal compliance, while threats include resistance to change and competition. To address these challenges, increased efforts and collaboration are needed to minimize limitations and balance the trade-offs of these solutions. The goal is to improve the value proposition and create a marketing campaign that highlights the potential benefits, including economic and productivity benefits, reduced risk of legal non-compliance, and market differentiation.

According to the basic principles for Exploitation, the Exploitation plan should demonstrate a connection between the proposed activities and the expected impact of the SPATIAL project. Activities and outcomes that have been articulated and described served as an intake for a new assessment of the impact the project is set out to have after the end of the funding period will be achieved.

The BFMULO analysis specified the exploitation expectations, claims and aims of each partner forming the starting point for the IPR protection guidance as well as for defining partners' individual exploitation plans.

The final sections outline exploitation activities that will be carried out in the following phase of the project including further development of the plan and related frameworks.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AUS	Australo Marketing company
BFMULO	Background-Foreground-Making-Using-Licensing-Other
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
eCall	Emergency Call
ER	Exploitable Results
EU	European Union
EUR	Erasmus University Rotterdam
FOKUS	Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems
GDPR	General Data protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IT	Information Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
KER	Key Exploitation Results
ML	Machine Learning
MFX	Mainflux Labs
MI	Montimage EURL
MINI	MinnaLearn
NG112	Next Generation 112
NEC	NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH
TEE	A trusted execution environment
TID	Telefónica I+D
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TUD	Delft University of Technology
UCD	University College Dublin
UT	Unversity Tartu
XAI	Explainable AI, or Interpretable AI, or Explainable Machine Learning
WSC	WithSecure - provider of security services

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1 INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) is focused on maintaining its technological leadership and promoting economic growth with sustainable goals, green industry, and job creation through initiatives such as Horizon 2020. This research and innovation framework program encourages collaboration between science, industry, and public institutions to advance knowledge and innovation. It is essential for the results and knowledge gained from the projects to be transferred, disseminated, and commercialized to achieve EU goals. Participation in Horizon 2020 requires recipients to fulfill their commitment to commercialize and publicize the results of the funded projects. The Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation working package is established for this purpose and involves preparing project participants for the commercialization of project outcomes through exploitation plans. The exploitation plans must take into account the interests of all consortium partners and fulfill the expectations for the project outcomes.

SPATIAL Project Objectives

SPATIAL project in general aims to achieve one of the top priorities in Europe, which is trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. With a special focus on trustworthiness in the cyber security domain, SPATIAL project objectives are:

- 1) To develop systematic verification and validation software/hardware mechanisms that ensure AI transparency and explainability in security solution development;
- 2) To develop system solutions, platforms, and standards that enhance resilience in the training and deployment of AI in decentralized, uncontrolled environments;
- 3) To define effective and practical adoption and adaptation guidelines to ensure streamlined implementation of trustworthy AI solutions;
- 4) To create educational modules that provide technical skills, ethical and socio-legal awareness to current and future AI engineers/developers to ensure the accountable development of security solutions;
- 5) To develop a communication framework that enables an accountable and transparent understanding of AI applications for users, software developers and security service providers.

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1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

The purpose of this deliverable report is to create an initial Exploitation plan for the project SPATIAL outcomes and results. As such it is part of the working package WP6 Impact, Outreach and Collaboration and its Task 6.3 Innovation Management, Exploitation and Sustainability.

This deliverable aims to:

- Disclose the initial exploitation strategy, objectives and plan of the project
- Outline overview of the project technology background, ie. EU strategies, technology, markets, sectors, major players, and target groups that are relevant to project exploitation
- Identify consolidated and refined exploitation results, which will be created in the project, the value and benefits they provide for the target groups as well as their routes of exploitation
- Serve as an instrument and exploitation and commercialization guideline for SPATIAL project partners
- Confirm that exploitable results will be utilized and required project impact is achieved
- Introduce preliminary IPR choices/preferences regarding the project results amongst de partners
- Serve as an initial work-in-progress document that will be developed further in the following years of the project
- To manage the exploitation of the results and knowledge produced by the project

1.2 INTENDED READERSHIP

As a public document, this report is available to all interested parties and stakeholders. His primary purpose is to provide understanding and guidelines for the exploitation process and activities to SPATIAL project partners. However, the report can act as an exploitation channel and instrument itself to all relevant external stakeholders - who might be interested in project outcomes - considering that it provides important information on the benefits and values that project results and outcomes provide.

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1.3 RELATIONSHIP WITH OTHER DELIVERABLES

This deliverable is connected to Deliverable “D6.1 SPATIAL Impact Master Plan” whose goal was to outline a master plan for dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies as well as “D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Interim Report”, which documents measures carried out through the first period of the project. Dissemination and communication activities that raise awareness of the project results and promote action itself to relevant and diverse stakeholder groups are laying the necessary foundation and ground for the exploitation activities.

In this initial phase of planning, this deliverable also draws from the technical aspects and descriptions from Deliverable “D1.1 Requirements Analysis For AI Towards Addressing Security Risks and Threats To System and Network Architectures” in which testing and the difficulty of certification and standardization are covered as related to the project results that addressed these issues directly and with “D2.1 Existing AI Algorithms and Their Accountability and Resilience Features” within the context of applications to IoT, 5G, and cybersecurity.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial intelligence (AI) is proving to be a double-edged sword. While this can be said of most new technologies, both sides of the AI blade are far sharper, and neither is well understood.- Benjamin Cheatham, McKinsey & Company [1]

AI can be described as a set of advanced general-purpose technologies that employ methods from statistics, computer science, and cognitive psychology to enable computers to effectively perform highly complex tasks. It is becoming one of the most important technologies that will transform every sector of the economy, science, culture, and society, in a way that previous general-purpose technologies had done. Regarding the business realm, although it is already in use in thousands of companies around the world in a number of practical applications, its significant impact is expected to come in the following years.

The primary technology that is behind AI's dramatic outcome that is happening in the last few years is the machine learning technique called deep learning or deep neural networks. A subset of AI, Machine learning is the convergence of computer science and statistics where algorithms are used to conduct a given task without being explicitly programmed; rather, they identify patterns in the data and generate predictions as soon as relevant and new data is received. Deep learning is an advanced machine-learning technique based on the use of multilayered artificial neural networks roughly similar to the biological neural networks of the

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human brain. It is important to emphasize that broader technological development that enabled machine learning and deep learning applications are powerful computers and a vast amount of data that is possible to collect across all industry sectors.

AI Advantages

The benefits of AI are multifold with myriad applications in industry manufacturing (predictive maintenance, quality control), telecommunications (customer behavior analysis, network optimization), finance (fraud detection, risk management), energy and utilities (energy consumption analysis, and demand forecasting), transportation and logistics (autonomous vehicles and route optimization), marketing and advertising (personalized marketing, and sentiment analysis), retail (supply chain optimization, and inventory management), healthcare (medical imaging, drug discovery, and remote patient monitoring), the public sector (fraud detection, biometrics) and finally security and surveillance (fraud detection, intrusion detection, and biometrics). In general, AI excels in complex problem-solving, data analysis and decision-making in scope, speed and accuracy which transcends human capacity on a far-reaching and immense level. Finding the best solutions for addressing problems and challenges, generating incalculable insights predicting scenarios and outcomes, all with precision and an astonishing rate provides significant benefits in increased efficiency and productivity, optimizing operations, improving quality and time and resource savings. An additional important advantage of AI is its implementation in advanced robotics where these machines, embedded with extraordinary capabilities, replace humans in dangerous and hazardous operations like coal mining, bomb defusing, ocean and space exploring, chemical production processes, etc. Finally, AI is automating repetitive (often mundane) jobs, freeing up human resources and enabling the utilization of creative capacities and engagement in more important activities.

AI Challenges

However, experience has proved that AI brings very significant risks that cannot be disregarded. In the introduction section, these major risks and challenges associated with AI technology are outlined. Here, however, a detailed description is provided based on useful categorization outlined by the Wharton University Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning Risk & Security Working Group (AIRS) [2].

The risks that can outcome in potential damage and harm to organizations, citizens, or society, in general, can be summarized as following. The potential risks associated with artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) systems can be grouped into four categories: inadequate governance, potential AI/ML attacks, testing and trust, and compliance. Inadequate governance can result from a lack of traceability in AI implementation, poor data quality, and limitations in training systems. Potential AI/ML attacks include data privacy breaches, data poisoning, adversarial inputs, and model extraction. Testing and trust challenges include difficulties in understanding black box algorithms, bias in AI systems, and incorrect output due to the dynamic nature of AI/ML systems. Finally, compliance is a concern as AI/ML technologies

present new challenges for regulators, and organizations must consider the impact of AI implementations on existing policies.

2.2 CYBERSECURITY

If cybercrime was a country in 2017, it would have the 13th highest GDP in the world, between South Korea and Australia. - McBride, S. Cybersecurity Magazine

Protection and defense of computers, computer systems and digital networks referred to as cybersecurity in technical terms, shifted out of the domain of technical experts and specialists many years ago.

From identity checks and methods required for applications that we use in our daily lives and work to massive payment card details stealing, ransomware attacks on companies and public institutions, publicly exposing victims' internal and private information and communications, and industrial or state-sponsored espionage, issues of cybersecurity became part of our daily lives. The advancement of the internet and omnipresent digitalization in both our professional and personal lives brought cybersecurity problems that are multiplying and broadening in every possible way.

With every new digital innovation arrives new possibilities for cybercrime. As the rate of technological development continues to accelerate, so does the rate of new cybersecurity threats. Cybersecurity seems like a never-ending race, the new capabilities and conveniences that the latest technologies are offering deliver new risks.

The emergence of the Internet of things and smart devices, for example besides enormous benefits, opened tremendous risks. Now, once isolated and unhackable machines are replaced with the ones that can potentially be controlled by hackers because they are embedded with connectivity and digital equipment which provide the possibility to do so. Advanced technologies provided the possibility for a wider partner ecosystem. As organizations work with more partners and third-party vendors, they may be exposed to new vulnerabilities through these partnerships.

The pandemic accelerated the shift towards remote work which has expanded the attack surface by introducing new devices and networks into the mix, such as employee home networks and personal devices.

The adoption of new technologies such as 5G networks and the pervasive transition to cloud services can also create new vulnerabilities and expand the attack surface [3].

Cryptocurrencies, on the other hand, have enabled cybercriminals with the possibility to earn money through cybercrime and enhance their ability to remain hidden while doing so, like never before. It was always difficult for criminals to receive payments since the account from which

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they ultimately took the funds could frequently be linked to them. These dangers are effectively reduced by cryptocurrencies. Additionally, the accessibility and global liquidity of cryptocurrencies have aided criminals in the laundering of money gained through a variety of criminal activities.

In general, as the complexity and interdependence between them arise, it increases the technological difficulty of safeguarding them. It also complicates non-technical security operations by increasing the number of individuals and organizations involved in defense.

Moreover, attackers no longer consist solely of individual criminals, but also of highly complex organizations that employ sophisticated advanced tools and capabilities with artificial intelligence and machine learning. The scale of the threat is spreading, and there is no organization that is immune to it.

According to the Cybercrime Magazine article "Cybercrime To Cost The World \$10.5 Trillion Annually By 2025" if cybercrime was a country in 2017, it would have the 13th highest GDP in the world, between South Korea and Australia. "If it were measured as a country, then cybercrime – which is predicted to inflict damages totaling \$6 trillion USD globally in 2021 – would be the world's third-largest economy after the U.S. and China." The same article predicts that the number will grow to \$10.5 trillion by 2025 [4].

However, while technical details and methods rapidly change with new technological developments, the motivations and goals of attackers and perpetrators have been and stay the same. It can be easily classified, in cybercrime where the goal is simply money, then attacks that aim to publicly humiliate their victims, industrial espionage in which companies are trying to discover sensitive information about their competitors, and finally state-sponsored cyber warfare which can be divided further into espionage and sabotage.

2.3 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR CYBERSECURITY

Cyber hygiene, patching vulnerabilities, security by design, threat hunting, and machine learning-based artificial intelligence are mandatory prerequisites for cyber defense against the next generation threat landscape. -James Scott, Professor of Statistics and Data Science, University of Texas

The previous section outlined how the increasing complexity and interconnectivity of modern networks and systems have led to the realization that advanced digital technologies, while driving value, also create new vulnerabilities with the expansion of surfaces for cyber attacks. Furthermore, security teams, which are often understaffed, are struggling to keep up with the vast amount of data from various sources, numerous tools, and a lack of insights. These

challenges are too difficult for even the leading security experts and the largest cybersecurity teams.

Finally, continuously changing their methods and operations, cyber attackers now also employ AI technologies to identify vulnerabilities and conduct more effective assaults. This makes staying ahead of them even more difficult.

However, the utilization of AI for cybersecurity solutions which is in consideration for more than a decade has become a reality. According to an IBM report, the use of AI in security operations is becoming increasingly common, with 93% of executives reporting that they are either already utilizing AI for security operations or are planning its implementation with "65% of adopters report that this application of AI has had a significant positive impact on their security operations [5].

With its pervasive capabilities, AI is enhancing and significantly improving cybersecurity in numerous ways:

- **Increased efficiency and reduced workload for security specialists**
AI can automate many cybersecurity tasks that are currently performed manually, such as scanning for vulnerabilities or analyzing log files, freeing up time for security professionals to focus on more complex and important tasks. This can improve efficiency and productivity within the cybersecurity team as well as lead to cost savings for organizations.
- **Increased accuracy and speed in threat detection and response**
AI algorithms can analyze vast amounts of data and identify patterns and anomalies that may indicate a potential cyber attack. This allows for faster and more accurate detection of threats (fewer false positives and false negatives), which can lead to quicker response times and better protection against attacks.
- **Enhanced network security**
AI can continuously monitor systems and networks to identify vulnerabilities and threats providing real-time analysis of the situation and suggesting appropriate actions allowing organizations to quickly respond to any issues that may arise.
- **Enhanced data protection**
AI can help protect sensitive data by identifying and blocking unauthorized access attempts. It can also monitor data usage and alert security professionals if data is being accessed or transferred in an unauthorized manner.

- Increased adaptability with predictive analytics**
 AI can be used to analyze historical data and identify trends that may indicate a future cyber attack. This can allow cybersecurity systems to proactively defend against potential threats, rather than reacting after an attack has occurred.
- User behavior analysis**
 AI can be used to analyze user behavior and identify anomalies that may indicate a cyber threat. This can allow cybersecurity systems to identify and respond to threats that may not be detected by traditional security measures.
- Cybersecurity training**
 AI can be used to train cybersecurity professionals, by simulating cyber attacks and providing realistic training scenarios. This can help professionals develop the skills and knowledge they need to effectively defend against real-world threats.

[6][7][8][9][10][11]

2.4 EU STRATEGY, PRINCIPLES AND REGULATIONS FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The European Commission is dedicated to maintaining the EU's technological leadership and ensuring that new technologies serve all Europeans, improving their lives while preserving their rights. Among the technology areas of the Commission's strategy, Artificial Intelligence has particular importance considering that it will have a significant impact on nearly every sector of the economy. It already serves as the primary force behind developing technologies like big data, robotics, and the Internet of Things, and it will continue to do so for the foreseeable future [12].

According to McKinsey 2021 research AI adoption is continuing to rise steadily: 56 percent of all respondents report AI adoption in at least one function, up from 50 percent in 2020 [13].

Although Europe is at the forefront of using AI in manufacturing, in comparison to other parts of the world, Europe is still lagging behind in research and innovation. A total of €3.2 billion was invested in AI in Europe in 2016, compared to €12.1 billion in North America and €6.5 billion in Asia. In the context of this aggressive global competition Commission delivered a Strategy and Coordinated plan in 2018 to ensure the advancement, development and adoption of AI in Europe. In important areas like research, investment, market uptake, skills and talent, data, and international collaboration, this plan suggests almost 70 collaborative measures for stronger and more effective cooperation between Member States and the Commission [14].

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However, besides investment oriented-strategy, being dedicated to its fundamental values, the Commission is developing a regulatory approach which addresses the risk connected with utilization of AI technology.

These risks include:

- Lack of Implementation traceability
- Program bias in decision making
- Data sourcing and violation of personal privacy
- Lack of transparency (Black Box Algorithms)
- Unclear legal responsibility

As such they can cause a wide range of damages that can be both material (safety and health of people, including loss of life and property damage) and immaterial (loss of privacy, restrictions on the right to free expression, human dignity, and discrimination, for example in access to work).

These can be clearly violations of fundamental rights, such as the right to freedom of expression, freedom of assembly, human dignity, non-discrimination based on gender, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age, or sexual orientation, violation of personal data and private life, or the right to an effective judicial remedy and a fair trial, and in general imposing an impact on the core values upon which the EU is founded. This is why the EU commission, besides the strategy for maximizing the impact of investment in research, innovation, and deployment, has addressed socioeconomic aspects in parallel to enable the trustworthy and secure development of AI in Europe, and protect the values and rights of EU citizens.

In addition, the EU Commission formed a High-Level Expert Group, which issued “*Policy And Investment Recommendations For Trustworthy AI*” in April 2019, which proposed seven key requirements guidelines:

- Human agency and oversight
- Technical robustness and safety
- Privacy and data governance
- Transparency
- Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
- Societal and environmental wellbeing, and
- Accountability [15]

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2.5 SPATIAL PROJECT OBJECTIVES

AI's ubiquitous potential to have a significant impact on nearly every sector includes cybersecurity and in recent years it is becoming a necessary tool for improving the effectiveness of IT security teams.

AI can provide more efficient critical analysis and threat identification that security professionals need to reduce, because humans can no longer scale to adequately secure an enterprise-level attack surface. Additionally, AI can direct incident response, breach risk and improve security posture, find and prioritize hazards, and detect malware attacks before they happen.

Given the (Commission's) technology development strategies and goals, as well as the vast number and severity of cybersecurity attacks during the last years, cybersecurity has also emerged as a critical issue for the European Union (EU).

However, EU Commission is firmly dedicated to Trustworthiness as the principal foundation on which AI solutions can be developed, deployed, and utilized with a special emphasis on the cybersecurity domain. In this sense, the Commission has defined three fundamental pillars of trustworthy AI: it must be lawful, ethical, and robust. It is evident that as the complexity of AI increases, each of the three pillars alone is insufficient to establish trust in AI both individually and collectively.

Therefore, the SPATIAL project aims to develop concrete strategies and technologies that integrate these pillars and specifically focus on enhancing privacy, accountability, and resilience in AI to establish a trustworthy AI system.

Nevertheless, a major concern in the security of AI-based solutions in general and especially for cyber-physical systems is the opacity of algorithms, i.e., black box and lack of transparency resulting from their complexity and the fact that the behavior of these solutions depends not only on design choices but also on the training data that iteratively adjusts the algorithms and models after production. This makes it difficult, first to understand and explain how certain results are achieved and second to identify which data were used to reach particular decision outcomes and to quantify data security and privacy impacts throughout the process.

All of these led SPATIAL researchers to the conclusion that appropriate metrics and dedicated accountable measures are prerequisites for meaningful explanations, correction mechanisms, or ascertaining faults of AI algorithms. But, these uncertainties in AI and the opacity of data processing algorithms necessitate significant R&D efforts in data privacy, resilience engineering, and legal-ethical accountability. Consequently, the SPATIAL project aims to address these concerns by developing methods for making AI algorithms more transparent

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and explainable, as one of the means to achieve accountability and increase trust in AI-based solutions.

As a result, SPATIAL aims to contribute to the subject of accountability through research techniques, frameworks, and algorithms for the explainability of AI-based components. Therefore within the SPATIAL project, these terms were defined: i) "privacy" refers to the appropriate handling of data, including consent, notice, preservation mechanisms, and regulatory obligations; (ii) "resilience" refers to the ability of ICT systems to produce the intended outcome continuously despite failures or crises (e.g., cyber attacks or security breaches); and (iii) "accountability" is a legal and ethical obligation for an individual or organization that develops or deploys AI solutions to accept responsibility for them and to disclose the results in a transparent manner (i.e. explainability).

Here is very important to refer to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as an EU regulation that came into effect in 2018. One of GDPR's key principles is accountability, which gives individuals the right to an explanation when using computer algorithms. Explainability within AI accountability indicates the degree to which the internal workings of a machine-learning system can be understood and explained in terms that are meaningful to humans.

FIGURE 1: SPATIAL PILLARS -ACCOUNTABILITY, PRIVACY AND RESILIENCE

In that context in which the EU objective is to support Trustworthy AI, the SPATIAL project goal is to develop mechanisms, verification methods, and guidelines for trustworthy AI solutions in the cybersecurity domain.

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SPATIAL will concentrate on two major topics:

1. How to secure AI-driven ICT systems
- and
2. How to improve AI-powered security solutions in terms of accountability, privacy, and resilience.

The first "how-to" will address data bias/poisoning, while the second "how to" will focus on black-box AI in security solutions.

Secure AI-driven ICT systems and	Data bias/poisoning
AI-powered security solutions in terms of accountability, privacy, and resilience	Black-box AI in security solutions.

TABLE 1: SPATIAL TOPICS

The problems that will be solved extend from the lower algorithmic/software level to the fundamental hardware level, such as Trusted Execution Environment.

The following SPATIAL goals and concrete steps to attain them are planned:

- 1) To develop systematic verification and validation software/hardware mechanisms that ensure AI transparency and explainability in security solution development;
- 2) To develop system solutions, platforms, and standards that enhance resilience in the training and deployment of AI in decentralized, uncontrolled environments;
- 3) To define effective and practical adoption and adaptation guidelines to ensure streamlined implementation of trustworthy AI solutions;
- 4) To create educational modules that provide technical skills, ethical and socio-legal awareness to current and future AI engineers/developers to ensure the accountable development of security solutions;
- 5) To develop a communication framework that enables an accountable and transparent understanding of AI applications for users, software developers and security service providers.

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Effective and practical adoption and adaptation guidelines for software developers to ensure streamlined implementation of trustworthy AI in cybersecurity.

In order to validate development according to these objectives SPATIAL project will employ practical use cases pertaining to the application of AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity.

- Use Case 1: Privacy-preserving AI on the cloud-fog-edge continuum,
- Use Case 2: improving the explainability, resilience and performance of cybersecurity in 4G/5G/6G and Internet of Things (IoT) networks,
- Use Case 3: Accountable AI in Emergency eCall System: the utilization of accountable AI in next-generation emergency communication and
- Use Case 4: resilient cybersecurity analysis based on machine learning models

3 EXPLOITATION PRINCIPLES, OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The introduction section explained the strategic and integral importance of dissemination and exploitation of results from research and innovation projects for the success of the Horizon 2020 program and its achievement of economic, social, and environmental impacts. For this reason, each partner is required to develop Plan of Exploitation and Dissemination of Results or PEDR, a document that describes how the partners intend to exploit and disseminate the results of the project both while it is still being worked on and after it has been completed. It is important to emphasize the difference between required activities, considering that this document is elaborating Exploitation plans.

The following table outlines the difference between dissemination, communication and exploitation:

- **Dissemination** - Public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium, a process of promotion and raising awareness to various stakeholder groups
- **Communication** - Strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.
- **Exploitation** - Exploitation is referred to by the European Commission as:

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“The utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.”

What is actually the "result" in this context? The definition of the EU Commission is wide, and refers to *“any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights”*.

According to these definitions, it is also necessary to highlight the distinction between market-oriented and research-oriented exploitation.

In the document published by the EU commission: *“Innovation How to convert Research into Commercial Success Story? Part 3: Innovation Management for Practitioners”* market-oriented exploitation is defined as *“any exploitation process of research outcome that has a commercial objective and contributes to gaining or increasing profits and/or economic (i.e. market-related) competitiveness”*[16].

Research-oriented exploitation, on the other hand, aimed at further research activities also includes the transfer of knowledge and its dissemination in relevant events and publications. Above mentioned importance of exploitation activities is evident from the requirements articulated and formalized in the research and innovation projects' General Agreements between the European Commission and the Consortiums responsible for the implementation of the projects.

Particularly for the SPATIAL project, according to the Grant Agreement (art. 45) exploitation is in fact a compulsory activity, as each beneficiary must –up to four years after the period set out at end of the project –take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing).

Exploitation measures accepted by the Commission include:

- (a) using results in further research activities (outside the action);
- (b) developing, creating, or marketing a product or process;
- (c) creating and providing a service, and
- (d) using results in standardization activities.

Additionally, the basic principles of exploitation activities are also defined and are as follows:

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- a) Exploitation (dissemination and communication) plan should demonstrate a connection between the proposed activities and the expected impact of the SPATIAL project
- b) Exploitation plan must have clear objectives adapted to the relevant target users
- c) Exploitation plan must include a strategy for the exploitation of results.

3.1 EXPLOITATION OBJECTIVES

The general objective for the SPATIAL project result exploitation is to implement a coherent exploitation strategy throughout the project and to support the beneficiaries in the coordination and production of their exploitation activities in order to achieve successful exploitation and adoption of results and benefits.

In particular, the objectives of the SPATIAL Exploitation plan are:

- To develop and maintain effective exploitation methods
- To facilitate timely communication and alignment between the partners regarding the exploitation strategy
- To define the market potential and the target entities
- To identify the SPATIAL partner's exploitations results and their value for the relevant target entities
- To define the partners' exploitation strategies

3.2 EXPLOITATION METHODOLOGY

In the *D6.1 SPATIAL Impact Master plan* submitted in M06 of the project, the Exploitation methodology is briefly outlined. In this section, however, as an integral aspect of the strategy for the current phase of the project, the methodology is refined with additional elements and described in greater detail in order to lay the ground for a full understanding of completed activities and their outcomes.

Development of the internet and digital technologies in the past decades brought the expansion of innovative products, solutions, services and processes, whether there were carried out by established companies or startups driven by entrepreneurial endeavor. The business domain

similar to science has already developed extensive knowledge, methodologies, analytical and other models, tools and frameworks in order to achieve rigor, precision, and certainty in order to achieve planned and expected results.

On the other hand, entrepreneurship as a realm and phenomenon which can be roughly described as the creation of new businesses, new products, solutions and services, was neglected in that sense.

As Steve Blank, an adjunct professor at Stanford University have stated in the article "*Why the Lean Start-Up Changes Everything*" for Harvard Business Review:

"Launching a new enterprise—whether it's a tech start-up, a small business, or an initiative within a large corporation—has always been a hit-or-miss proposition."[17]

However, the advancement of new technologies and initiatives founded on them brought the development of many methodologies, frameworks, and tools for accessing many aspects of entrepreneurship. All of these are utilized to examine the success of a newly conceived product or business model as a large hypothesis that must be tested from many angles. Its probability on the market (market-fit), time, human and financial resources required for its development, marketing and promotional strategies, prospective and risk of competition or alternatives that already exist on the market, communication approaches to target customers and audiences and many more.

Many researchers around the world were involved in the development of these practices. Though, the above-mentioned professor Steve Blank, with his comprehensive *Customer Development* methodology, and researchers from the University of Lausanne with *Business Model Canvas* and *Value proposition Canvas* models, are pioneers and at the forefront of "a scientific approach to launching a new enterprise."

For the purpose of the Exploitation of SPATIAL results numerous methodologies and tools are introduced, including *Business Model Canvas* and *Value proposition Canvas* models whose purpose is to ensure that scientific, economic, or public stakeholders obtain the greatest benefit from the commercialization, usage, and long-term sustainability of SPATIAL research, thereby translating R&I activities into tangible value and effect for society.

SPATIAL Exploitation methodology is a multi-stage process, structured in regard to the dynamics of SPATIAL project development and periodic interim reports in two following phases.

I phase M1 - M18 of the project

1. Market research and Market Readiness Assessment
2. Consolidation of project partners' individual exploitation results and their initial exploitation intents with the exploitation matrix tool
3. Creation of Value proposition for project partners' individual exploitation results, facilitated with a dedicated workshop and using Value Proposition Canvas model
4. Creation of partners' business models facilitated with a dedicated workshop and using the Business model Canvas tool
5. Identification of partners' exploitation expectations, claims, and objectives as the foundation for both the IPR protection guidance and the definition of each partner's specific exploitation strategy using the BFMULO tool (background-foreground-making-using-licensing-other).
6. Exploitation strategy recommendations using Richard P. Rumelt's strategy kernel framework

FIGURE 2: EXPLOITATION - I PHASE _M1 -M18

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II phase M19 – M36 of the project

7. LinkedIn group utilization as a form of community for two-way communication with stakeholders
8. Creation of value propositions and business model generation for SPATIAL use cases
9. Implementation of *B2B Elements of Value* framework on articulated value propositions
10. Business plan creation for each partner and SPATIAL use cases
11. Indicative Social Return on Investment (SROI)
12. Identification of purchasing key decision-makers expected in target entities with Buying persona Canvas and importance attributes per role diagram
13. Assessment of the SPATIAL project impact in relation to identified results and activities
14. Introduction of the Go-to-Market plan

FIGURE 3: EXPLOITATION - II PHASE _M19 -M36

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3.2.1 MARKET RESEARCH AND MARKET READINESS ASSESSMENT

Market Readiness Assessment. A planning tool that will include periodic (re-)assessments combined with goal-setting future scores of the project based on several indicators, Project Market Background, Barriers and risks for exploitation, Opportunities and growth strategy.

3.2.2 CONSOLIDATION OF PROJECT PARTNER'S INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATIONS RESULTS AND THEIR INITIAL EXPLOITATION INTENTS WITH THE EXPLOITATION MATRIX TOOL

The proposal phase requires the initial identification of project results (KER), as well as individual exploitation results intentions of each partner.

However, as the experience of H2020 projects has demonstrated, the significant insights and knowledge gained throughout the research, exchange, and collaboration during the project's implementation provide the opportunity for a better understanding and assessment of project results that can be exploited by partners or external stakeholders, as well as an exploitation strategy.

For that purpose, the exploitation matrix tool is used with the goal to support partners to consolidate and refine their exploitation results and intentions.

The exploitations matrix is a table that consists of the following sections:

KER Column for identification of new and refined results:

- **Role In Exploitation**
 - *Owner*
Developer of exploitable result
 - *Beneficiary*
Partner interested in exploiting a result produced by the project / other partners without the direct contribution
- **Target Sector**
Requires identification of partners' planned target sector of application
- **Target Audience**
Requires description of partners' specific Target users/clients/audience for Exploitation activity

- **Characterization of Exploitation**

As indicated at the beginning of this section, exploitation can generally be divided into two categories: market-oriented and research-oriented. This column, however, provides a more accurate categorization that can better support the exploitation strategy and operations.

- *Commercial or market-oriented exploitation*
Indicates any process of exploitation of research results that has a commercial objective, which means that it ultimately strives towards or helps to the gaining or raising of profits and/or economic / market competitiveness
- *Research & Development (R&D) exploitation*
By engaging in new projects, (EU-funded or sponsored by other instances) based on the knowledge and experience gained in the SPATIAL project
- *Scientific exploitation*
Involves further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned or publishing of certain results of the project
- *Educational exploitation results*
Used for training and/or educational purposes
- *Knowledge transfer*
From academia to academia or/and industry or /and regulators
- *Contributions to open-source projects and standardization*
Offering public access and promoting its widespread use in commercial and public adoption in commercial and public systems for interested parties
- *Community exploitation*
Around the topics of the project, raising awareness for the addressed problems and the proposed solutions
- *Policy exploitation*
This involves the standardization or reform of rules and regulations

- **Exploitation routes for results**

This column should provide an answer to a simple question of what will happen to the project's findings or in which form they will be offered to targeted stakeholders.

- *Developing and selling own products /solutions through direct sale, distributor, licensing, online service-fee mode / Software as a service (SaaS)*

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- *Consulting services*
- *Technology services*
- *Training services*
- *Educational courses*
- *Spin-Off activities*
- *Cooperation agreement/Joint Ventures*
- *Selling IP right/Selling the (IP-based) business*
- *Licensing IP rights (out-licensing)*
- *Standardization activities (new standards/ongoing procedures)*
- *Use for further research*

An additional part of the matrix is offered for industrial partners who have clear market-oriented exploitation intentions.

It consists of two columns:

- Possible competitors

For identification of competitors in the market or expected to enter it: who are the potential competitors, what do they offer, in which sectors and which target

- Possible market barriers

For a description of barriers that the product/service may encounter while positioning in the market and having the potential to affect its market penetration. Examples "lack of awareness about the need for such a product/service"; "potential not perceiving the value of the service"; "high costs of commercialization"; or "high level of novelty of the product" in case of research breakthroughs or radical innovations.

3.2.3 CREATION OF VALUE PROPOSITIONS FOR PROJECT PARTNERS' INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION RESULTS, FACILITATED WITH A DEDICATED WORKSHOP AND USING VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS MODEL

After consolidation and refinement of partners' individual exploitation results and intentions, the next step is to identify and articulate actual benefits and value that these results can provide for target entities and stakeholders.

Value proposition Canvas model is used for this purpose. This model facilitates insight and understanding for each partner, precisely how their intended results provide benefit and value

for target entities and stakeholders, why they would use these results, what benefits they can expect, or what problem they can solve or gain an advantage from them. Here is a crucial distinction between the description of results and the value it provides for the target stakeholders. Within the Value proposition canvas, the identification of results benefits, and the value they bring consists of two steps.

The first step is understanding of Customer/ Target entity profile, in three basic aspects:

FIGURE 4: VALUE PROPOSITION -THE FIRST STEP

The second step is an assessment of the value map for the exploitation results.

THE SECOND STEP - Value Proposition Canvas

FIGURE 5. VALUE PROPOSITION - THE SECOND STEP

3.2.4 CREATION OF PARTNERS' BUSINESS MODELS FACILITATED WITH A DEDICATED WORKSHOP AND USING THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS TOOL

The business model canvas was created by the University of Lausanne and originated from the Ph.D. thesis "*The Business Model Ontology - a proposition in a design science approach.*"[18]

This model has been utilized across the globe, and it is already being utilized by businesses such as 3M, Intel, SAP, Microsoft, Ericsson, Deloitte, and IBM, countless startups, and public institutions like Government Services of Canada, and it is recognized in EU H2020 programs.

It consists of 9 critical elements that serve to systematically address and take into consideration hypothesis or assumptions about how the organization plans to generate revenue or value in social, cultural, or other contexts.

These nine elements are:

1. Customer segments

A different group of target entities, organizations, customers, or people, that enterprise tries to reach. In the context of the SPATIAL project, this is related to the question, of to whom exploitation results can provide benefits and value.

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2. Value Propositions

This segment is covered especially with a workshop utilizing Value proposition Canvas (created by the same researchers from the University of Lausanne) because it is an essential and most challenging aspect. It simply has to provide an answer to what benefits and value individual partners' exploitation results can provide for target entities and stakeholders.

3. Channels

In the context of SPATIAL, this is the issue or pathways i.e., channels through which target entities are reached.

4. Customer Relationships

How partners will get their target entities, and how they will keep target entities and stakeholders using SPATIAL results, are questions related to this element.

5. Revenue Streams

The mode in which partners intend to make revenue with exploitation results. This aspect is covered in the Consolidation of project partners' individual exploitation results stage, namely exploitation routes.

However, there to basic modes of revenue streams that have to be addressed as basic categories:

- a) Transaction revenues resulting from one-time customer payments
- b) Recurring revenues resulting from ongoing payments or post-purchase customer support.

6. Key Resources

This element has to provide identification of key resources whether they are human, financial, or physical required for the creation of the value or benefit for target entities.

7. Key Activities

In the SPATIAL project context, this element should address the most important activities in relation to the development of exploitation results.

8. Key Partnerships

Answers, who are the key partners needed for the creation of exploitable results?

9. Cost Structure

Outlines the most important costs required for the development and further exploitation of SPATIAL results.

3.2.5 IDENTIFICATION OF PARTNERS' EXPLOITATION EXPECTATIONS, CLAIMS, AND OBJECTIVES

Analysis with the **BFMULO** tool serves to determine partners' exploitation expectations, claims and objectives regarding IPR protection guidance and partner's specific exploitation strategy.

BFMULO refers to:

- **B** = IPR's on background information, information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.
- **F** = IPR's on foreground information, Information including all kind of exploitable results generated by the project partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project. To have an F in an exploitable result it is necessary that a partner has a task(s) in the project related to that very result.
- **M** = Making the products, manufacturing and selling or directly implementing it through own facilities and skills.
- **U** = Using the result, implemented with own knowledge to develop new ranges of products or newer processing. Furthermore, the direct or indirect utilization of foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.
- **L** = Licensing the result, therefore earning from a negotiation towards third parties outside the Consortium.
- **O** = Other, any other exploitation means (e.g.: consultancy, provide services, etc).

3.2.6 LINKEDIN GROUP UTILIZATION

The utilization of the LinkedIn group as a form of community that enables two-way communication is planned in order to provide several benefits for the SPATIAL project. These benefits include:

Raising awareness and branding of the SPATIAL project and its members as forerunners of the development of resilient, trustworthy explainable methods and solutions for AI-based cybersecurity systems.

Networking and building relationships with relevant stakeholders and target entities that can be potential customers or beneficiaries of SPATIAL project results.

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Encouraging engagement and feedback that can be valuable for the project development as well as for dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

Keeping up with other similar developments that can be useful to the project and its goals.

And finally, a LinkedIn group can serve as an **additional platform for sharing SPATIAL research results and findings**.

3.2.7 VALUE PROPOSITIONS AND BUSINESS MODEL GENERATION FOR SPATIAL USE CASES

SPATIAL project plans the development of four use cases. Considering that these use cases are selected to "connect and promote business cases that are beneficial for EU industry and SMEs but also to preserve EU values" the articulation of their value proposition and business model generation is necessary.

3.2.8 IMPLEMENTATION OF "B2B ELEMENTS OF VALUE" FRAMEWORK ON ARTICULATED VALUE PROPOSITIONS

"B2B Elements of Value" framework is created by the renowned consulting firm Bain which analyzed scores of quantitative and qualitative customer studies conducted for their clients **over three decades**, aimed to understand what matters most to B2B buyers.

The research identified 40 fundamental "elements of value" that fall into five categories: table stakes, functional, ease of doing business, individual, and inspirational.

- Table stakes involve meeting basic requirements such as specifications, price, regulations, and ethical standards.
- Functional elements address companies' economic or product performance needs, such as cost reduction and scalability.
- Ease of doing business elements make it easier to conduct business and provide objective types of value time savings, reduced effort, or improving its operational performance like simplification, organization
- Individual elements address buyers' personal or career-related priorities, such as reduced anxiety, appealing design, and increased marketability.
- Inspirational elements improve the customer's vision of the future, provide hope for the future of the organization or individual buyers, or enhance a company's social responsibility [19].

Utilizing this framework SPATIAL partners should consider how value propositions can be tailored to address value in all of these areas. With a clear and detailed map of all possible values important in B2B domain partners can better understand the unique needs and wants of their

target entities and customers' needs so they could build more compelling and differentiated value propositions.

Furthermore, in large organizations, many people are involved in making buying decisions, so it is always necessary to understand who is on buying team, who has influence and what priorities and sources of value for each. “B2B Elements of Value” framework can be used to align the value proposition to each member of this buying decision team.

3.2.9 INDICATIVE SOCIAL RETURN ON INVESTMENT (SROI)

The purpose of Indicative Social Return on Investment (SROI) in general is to assess the social impact and benefits of an investment or project. SROI aims to quantify the social impact of a project in financial terms, which makes it easier to compare the costs and benefits of different initiatives. In this way, SROI can provide decision makers with valuable information when choosing between different projects.

In the context of the SPATIAL project SROI can be useful for evaluating the impact of the project on society as a whole. By quantifying the expected social benefits of the project, SROI can help to determine the overall value of the project in terms of its potential impact on society.

3.2.10 BUSINESS PLAN CREATION

The exploitation plan also includes a business plan, a standard well-known instrument for determining the nature of an exploitation results market, identification of competitors, describing the sales and marketing strategy, and the financial background.

3.2.11 IDENTIFICATION OF KEY DECISION-MAKERS IN THE BUYING PROCESS

In the commercial exchange between organizations, commonly referred as business-to-business (B2B), it is an established fact that in the buying processes within one organization, it always participates and influences several of its members. In the final buying or purchasing decision, whether a product or service, are always members with financial expertise, members with technical expertise, and finally top management.

For the SPATIAL partners, this means a deeper understanding of their target entities and customers, in which values and benefits of the exploitation results should be tailored (if possible) to appropriately address key decision-makers in the buying or purchasing process.

For this purpose, a diagram for important attributes per role in the organization will be used or if it is possible, depending on partners' available information Buyer persona Canvas. A buyer persona is a detailed description of someone who represents the partner's target

audience. It contains demographic details, interests, and behavioral traits, goals, pain points, and buying patterns.

3.2.12 ASSESSMENT OF THE SPATIAL PROJECT IMPACT IN RELATION TO IDENTIFIED RESULTS AND ACTIVITIES

The exploitation plan needs to demonstrate a relationship between the activities that are going to be proposed and the expected impact of the SPATIAL project.

3.2.13 INTRODUCTION TO GO-TO-MARKET PLAN

In the final stage, SPATIAL partners will be introduced with a go-to-market plan, which they can utilize after the completion of the SPATIAL project.

The specific Go-to-market plan which will be used for this purpose is created by one of the most prominent venture capital firms, Andreessen Horowitz. The go-to-market plan is a part of Andreessen Horowitz's dedication to helping its portfolio companies grow their business [20].

4 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY AND ACTIVITIES

4.1 INITIAL ACTIVITIES AND IMPACT MASTER PLAN

The initial phase of Exploitation activities consisted of the "D6.1 Spatial Impact Master Plan" deliverable report which was successfully submitted on time on M06 of the project. This report in section "3 Exploitation And Sustainability" outlines the initial exploitation strategies for the project, including the difference between dissemination and communication activities, an overview of market domains and target groups, frameworks, methodologies and tools that will be utilized for the exploitation strategy and activities.

However, a number of other activities related to exploitation-related activities have been conducted and completed before and after this report, which are summarized below:

- The social media accounts of 27 World's Foremost Researchers and Entrepreneurs working in the field of AI and robotics. The selection is based on the insightful book "[Architects of Intelligence: The truth about AI from the people building it](#)" written by Martin Ford, a well-respected author in the field of artificial intelligence. By following their social media accounts,

LIST OF 27 WORLD'S FOREMOST AI RESEARCHERS
"OPINION LEADERS"

 David Ferrucci ^{3rd} Founder & CEO at Elemental Cognition Wilton, Connecticut, United States - Contact info	 Stuart Russell ^{2nd} Professor of Computer Science at UC Berkeley Berkeley, California, United States - Contact info	 Yann LeCun ^{3rd} VP & Chief AI Scientist at Meta Talks about #AI, #ML, #Facebook, #computervision New York, New York, United States - Contact info	 James Manyika SVP, Google: Technology and Society United States - Contact info	 Rodney Brooks ^{3rd} Artificial Intelligence and robotics San Francisco, California, United States - Contact info
 Yoshua Bengio ^{3rd} Full professor at Université de Montréal Montréal, Quebec, Canada - Contact info	 Daphne Koller ^{3rd} Founder and CEO, insitro (we're hiring!), insitro.com Professor of CS & Pathology at Stanford	 Daniela Rus ^{2nd} Deputy Dean of Research, Schwarzman College of Computing Massachusetts Institute of Technology	 Judea Pearl @judeapearl Student of causal Inference, human reasoning, through the sharp lens of artificial intelligence.	 Fei-Fei Li @dfefei Prof (CS @Stanford), Co-Director @Stanford4AI, Researcher #AI #computervision #ML #AI+health
 Bryan Johnson ^{2nd} Founder & CEO of Kernel Los Angeles County, California, United States	 Oren Etzioni ^{2nd} CEO, Allen Institute for AI	 Cynthia Breazeal ^{2nd} Founder & Chief Scientist at Jibo, Inc. Cambridge, Massachusetts, United States	 Jeff Dean ^{3rd} Google Senior Fellow at Google, Inc.	 Andrew Ng ^{3rd} Founder and CEO of Landing AI (We at AI Fund)

FIGURE 6: 27 WORLDS FOREMOST AI RESEARCHERS

the project partners can stay updated on the latest developments in the field and learn from their insights and perspectives.

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- Guidelines for effective posting on LinkedIn groups: The purpose of these guidelines is to provide tips and advice on how to effectively post on LinkedIn groups, in order to reach a wider audience and promote the project.
- 80 Companies list and their value proposition: This list provides information on 80 companies and their value proposition, and was created for the purpose of market research, refinement of the value proposition, and support for marketing and sales activities. It was generated based on the informative article by CB Insights, a leading market intelligence and data analytics firm, entitled "Cybersecurity's Next Frontier: 80+ Companies Using Artificial Intelligence To Secure The Future In One Infographic. The list is available as an Excel spreadsheet in the project's Emdesk database. An important finding from this initial research is that none of the companies surveyed provide features for trustworthy and explainable AI.

80 Companies Using Artificial Intelligence for Cybersecurity					
General information					
#	Company name	URL	Company description	HQ Country	Category
55	Seclytics	https://seclytics.com/	Seclytics is a one-stop cyber threat intelligence correlation and prediction platform. Leveraging security analytics and machine learning, Seclytics learns patterns in threats, then detects current attacks and predicts future attacks before they occur.	United States	Predictive Intelligence
56	SentinelOne	https://sentinelone.com/	SentinelOne (NYSE: S1) delivers autonomous endpoint protection through a single agent that prevents, detects, responds, and hunts attacks across all major vectors. Designed for ease of use, the S1 platform saves customers time and money.	United States	Predictive Intelligence
57	SignalSense	https://signalsense.com/	SignalSense is a technology company offering cloud-based advanced data collection and breach detection solutions that leverage machine learning.	United States	Predictive Intelligence
59	CyberSaint Security	https://cybersaint.io/	CyberSaint's solutions streamline the compliance process, increase visibility, and add clear metrics. The result is a more efficient process, and simplified reports that don't require an advanced degree in computer science to understand.	United States	Predictive Intelligence
60	Cyence	https://cyence.net/	Cyence empowers the insurance industry to understand the impact of cyber risk in the context of dollars and probabilities. Cyence's unique approach combines economic risk modeling, cybersecurity and big data analytics to create a comprehensive view of risk.	United States	Risk Management
61	Cytora	https://cytora.com/	Cytora provides AI-powered solutions for the commercial insurance industry. The company enables underwriting for commercial insurance via the Cytora API-enabled Underwriting Platform that allows insurers to underwrite more efficiently.	United States	Risk Management
62	Haystax Technology	https://haystax.com/	Haystax Technology is a security analytics platform provider. Its platform delivers advanced security analytics and risk-management solutions that enable rapid understanding and response to virtually any type of cyber or physical threat.	United States	Risk Management
63	Lexumo	https://lexumo.com/	Lexumo provides a cloud-based service that combines big data analytics with software analysis techniques to continuously search and index software to immediately identify publicly-known open source vulnerabilities that can be exploited.	United States	Risk Management
64	MetaCert	https://metacert.com/	MetaCert protects companies of all sizes from risks when using messaging apps. The Metacert Security Bot detects malware, phishing, and pornography in direct messages and Slack channels.	United States	Risk Management
65	Aware	https://awarehq.com/	Aware offers a risk management and analytics suite to address compliance, retention, archiving, litigation holds, eDiscovery, data governance, and human behavior risk within enterprise collaboration networks such as Slack, Microsoft Teams, and Yammer.	United States	Risk Management
66	ArmorWay	https://armorway.com/	ArmorWay provides a patented Artificial Intelligence (AI) platform that delivers descriptive, diagnostic, predictive and prescriptive analytics with cognitive intelligence and deep machine learning to dynamically understand and respond to threats.	United States	Risk Management
67	BehavioSec	https://behaviosec.com/	BehavioSec enables enterprises to transparently authenticate people across mobile and web apps by integrating its Behavioral Biometrics as a Service (BBaaS) platform. BehavioSec technology allows companies to continuously monitor and detect anomalous behavior.	United States	UEBA
68	CyberX	https://cyberx-labs.com/	CyberX is a unique product designed specifically for Industrial Internet networks. CyberX offers a platform for continuously reducing IOT and ICS risk and preventing costly production outages, safety failures, environmental incidents, and more.	United States	UEBA
69	Darktrace	https://darktrace.com/	Darktrace is a provider in intelligence-led Behavioral Cyber Defense that uses mathematics to automatically detect abnormal behavior in organizations in order to manage risks from cyber-attacks. Unlike software that reads log files or network traffic, Darktrace's AI learns the normal behavior of the network and detects anomalies in real-time.	United States	UEBA
70	E8 Security	https://e8security.com/	E8 Security provides security intelligence and analytics software. The company's system complements existing SIEM, IDS and other security tools by providing a scalable big data platform for long term data retention and retrospective analysis.	United States	UEBA
71	Exabeam	https://exabeam.com/	Exabeam complements existing security information and event management and log management systems with machine-learning technology that focuses on attacker behavior rather than malware and tools to detect modern threats.	United States	UEBA
72	Fortscale Security	https://fortscale.com/	Fortscale Security provides organizations with a platform combining predictive, big data analytics and advanced machine learning to give real-time visibility into the actions of users and entities across an environment and uncover anomalies.	United States	UEBA

FIGURE 7: 80 COMPANIES USING AI FOR CYBER SECURITY - EXCEL SHEET PRINTSCREEN

- Market research: This research, presented in [section 5](#), was conducted throughout the reporting period in parallel with other activities and was aligned in direction with those activities. Market research is fully presented in section 5 of this document.

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4.2 CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITION WORKSHOP FOR INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLANS

As indicated in section 3.2.2, the initial identification of KER and partner's individual exploitation results intentions, which is outlined in the proposal phase, usually come into reconsideration due to project development. That was the case in the SPATIAL project as well, where this development brought new understandings and knowledge gained throughout the research, discussions, first deliverables and workshops.

In the M15 of the project, partner MFX responsible for Exploitation WP6 and its tasks, provided to all partners the Exploitation Matrix document for Consolidation and refinement of Exploitation results.

Document consisted of:

- Individual Exploitations plans of each partner created in the project proposal - as a reminder
- Exploitation matrix table for the consolidation and refinement of consortium partner individual exploitation plan with simple instructions

These instructions included numerous characterizations of Exploitation that served as guidelines and directions for assisting partners in considering potential exploitation opportunities.

Consolidation and refinement of Exploitation results set the ground for the Value proposition workshop. The main purpose and objective of the workshop which took place on 25th November 2022, and was also coordinated by partner MFX, is the identification and articulation of the actual benefits and value that the intended exploitation results of each partner can provide for target entities and stakeholders. The workshop was facilitated with the Value Proposition Canvas model, a framework that was created by researchers from the University of Lausanne who also created a Business model Canvas. Prior to the workshop, MFX provided all partners with Value proposition canvas guidelines as support for a successful workshop.

The workshop was structured into 4 parts:

1. Introduction to the workshop

Part in which partners are presented with Value Proposition Canvas model principles and guidelines in order to provide a clear understanding of the mentioned model requirements.

2. Creation of a customer/target entity profile

All partners filled the section of the canvas which requires understanding and description of their customer/target entity profile in three basic aspects: customer’s/target entity’s job, pains and gains.

3. Creation of a value map for products/services/solution

This section requires partners' identification of benefits and value that their planned SPATIAL project results can provide to their customers/target entities. It consists also, of three basic aspects: Exploitation results, and their gain creators and pain relievers. The following are consolidated ER for each partner.

4. Concluding remarks

FIGURE 8: VALUE PROPOSITION WORKSHOP

These activities provided an opportunity to again recapitulate SPATIAL Key Exploitation Results (KER), which were initially formulated in the proposal phase.

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The table below summarizes SPATIAL KER:

No	Exploitable results	Partners	Exploitable route(s)
1	AI methods and algorithms enabling metrics of attack resilience and accountability; privacy protection; transparency and explainability; and certification	WSEC FOKUS TID TUD UCD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Consulting services ▸ Technology-based service development ▸ Training services ▸ Educational courses ▸ Use for further research ▸ Offer and supervise Master's theses and Bachelor's theses ▸ Standardization
2	Design and application of resilient AI algorithms, Explainable AI methods, and the design and realization of accountable and trustworthy AI-based systems.	TID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Aura (AI agent) ▸ Movistar TV recommender system ▸ Telefónica Tech (B2B AI services)
3	A prototype of an accountable and explainable AI-based emergency communication system that automatically detects emergencies and initiates emergency calls based on medical sensor data.	FOKUS	Use for further research
4	SaaS platform for secure multiparty computation and privacy-preserving AI/ML	MFX	PoCs and commercial deployments in the form of SaaS and customer private clouds (Technology services)
5	MMT security and performance monitoring framework with analytics based on XAI techniques for secure 5G/IoT networks	MMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Direct sale / distributor ▸ Licensing ▸ Online service-fee mode / Software as a service (SaaS) ▸ Consulting services ▸ Maintenance and support services ▸ Technology services ▸ Training services ▸ Use for further research

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6	Framework for verification and validation of software/hardware mechanisms, tools and system solution that will provide the critical building blocks for trustworthy AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity	UT	Foundation for engaging into other research projects; scientific publications; technical reports, and integration into educational curricula
7	Replication/cloning middleware for TEE-applications in cloud deployments	NEC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Improvement of current products ▸ Licensing
8	Highly engaging educational module that serves the needs of the academic and industry partners by bridging the gap between academic research and effective dissemination	MINI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Offering the course to existing customers as an upselling opportunity ▸ Approaching new customers interested in the field and topic ▸ Offering the module to other universities ▸ Encouraging existing students to take on the new course
9	Embedded socio-technical analysis	EUR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Training services ▸ Use for further research ▸ Policy recommendations

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF CONSOLIDATED SPATIAL EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

The outcomes from the Consolidation of Exploitation Results and Value Proposition workshop have been integrated into detailed tables for each partner, providing in-depth information on each partner's exploitation strategy. These tables can be found in Appendix A of this report and serve as a critical first step towards the successful exploitation of project results.

Outcomes of the Value proposition workshop can be utilized by SPATIAL partners in manifold ways but the most important are:

- Better identification and communication of the benefits of the SPATIAL results for targeted entities and stakeholders
- Development of a marketing, communication and sales strategy. By understanding their value proposition, SPATIAL partners can create an exploitation, marketing, and sales strategy that effectively communicates the value and the key benefits that should be highlighted across all available channels to attract and retain target entities and stakeholders.

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- Further improving SPATIAL results: Partners can use the insights i.e the needs and wants of their target entities, gained from the value proposition canvas to identify opportunities for improving their SPATIAL results to better meet those needs and direct the development of new products or services, or to improve existing ones.

4.3 BUSINESS MODEL GENERATION WORKSHOP AND INDIVIDUAL BUSINESS MODELS

After the Consolidation of Exploitation results and Value proposition workshop, partner MFX has organized a Business Model generation workshop which took place on December 15th, 2022.

Prior to the workshop, MFX again provided all partners with Business model generation canvas guidelines as support for a successful workshop.

The Business Model Generation Canvas model was employed in a workshop facilitated by a representative from partner MFX with the aim of systematically evaluating nine critical assumptions related to the generation of revenue or value in social, cultural, or other contexts from the results of the SPATIAL project. The introduction of the workshop was provided by the aforementioned representative, who also coordinated the workshop.

These nine critical elements include:

- Key Partners
- Cost structure
- Key Activities
- Key resources
- Value Propositions
- Customer Relationships
- Channels
- Revenue Streams

- Customer Segments

FIGURE 9: BUSINESS MODEL GENERATION WORKSHOP

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The outcomes of this workshop are presented for each SPATIAL partner in the following part of this section.

Individual canvases:

TU DELFT - 1

Delft University of Technology, the oldest and largest technology-focused university in the Netherlands is ranked 15th globally in the 2020 QS World University Rankings for Engineering Technologies. The Department of Engineering Systems and Services (ESS) and Intelligent Systems at TU Delft are taking part in the project and are dedicated to research in the areas of IoT, Explainable AI, edge computing, and cybersecurity.

Delft University of Technology is planning two different segments for its intended ER which then requires two business model generation canvases. The following one is for research communities.

Organisation: TU Delft Type of Organization: University	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<p>For the primary segment, TU delft identified research communities at, connected to, or impacted by research outcomes at TU Delft. This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › XAI researchers looking to create new ways of explaining machine learning algorithm behavior › Educators in AI fields › Researchers concerned with theoretical problems surrounding XAI <p>As the secondary segment, TU Delft recognized researchers and educators of external partners in the field of AI, in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › University of Helsinki › Umeå University › Tsinghua Beijing › TU Munich › HKUST 	<p>The value proposition for AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency, explainability and certification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Develop improved XUI elements to enhance interpretability on the user end › Analysis and streamlining of research framework nomenclature › Conceptualize enhanced causal models for accountability › Improved evaluation framework for assessing the interpretability of an explanation

Channels	Customer Relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Scientific dissemination through published papers, conferences and presentations. ‣ Internal workshops in TU Delft ‣ Updates on publications and workshops in social networks, such as LinkedIn ‣ Networking 	<p>The relationship with which TU Delft is planning to establish with identified segments relies on established academic networks i.e. research communities and dissemination networks (e.g. FCN network) and active communication and collaboration between individual researchers. The second is actually directed to TU Delft itself as a self-service via participation in open-source research.</p>
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<p>The only revenue stream planned for TU Delft is research grants.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Educational courses ‣ Furthering education at TU Delft from Masters and upward. ‣ Use for further research ‣ Continued dissemination and collaboration with internal and external academic elements
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<p>Key resources for the relevant critical elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Human resources, such as researchers to develop XAI platform ‣ and its rationale ‣ Research funding for enabling the human resources ‣ XAI platform and its metric 	<p>TU Delft is recognizing two major categories of partners, cooperative partners, which means internal and external departments/faculties with shared interests, and SPATIAL project partners.</p>
Cost structure	
<p>University costs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Researcher salaries ‣ Equipment/licenses costs ‣ Travel budgets 	

TABLE 3: TUD BUSINESS MODEL

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TU DELFT 2

The following and second Business Model Generation Canvas for TU Delft is aimed toward the healthcare sector.

Organisation: TU Delft Type of Organization: University	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<p>For the healthcare sector, TU Delft gave an additional explanation. Healthcare professionals use the outcome of AI algorithms in their diagnosis of certain ailments. Types of organizations include eldercare, remote care and hospitals. Within this segment, patients or other individuals who are impacted by the outcomes of AI methods and algorithms used by their healthcare provider. Finally, Stakeholders that are concerned with accountability such as healthcare authorities, policymakers or other governments aim to monitor the practices of healthcare providers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Improved XUI elements to enhance interpretability on the user end remote care, hospitals ▸ Tailored explanation process framework based on healthcare professional requirements ▸ Interpretability assessment targeting laypersons ▸ Improved parameters for interpretability and reevaluate existing XAI methods accordingly ▸ Enhanced causal models for accountability (e.g. lessons from critical realism)
Channels	Customer Relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Outreach between TU Delft and healthcare via its existing research channels as well as its new Healthcare section ▸ User studies targeting healthcare professionals as part of our research ▸ Scientific dissemination through normal channels (journals, conferences) 	<p>Self-service via partaking in open source research output (e.g. SPATIAL platform) Potential community formation as new developments at the TBM department of TU Delft aims to bridge the gap between the clinical health sector and TU Delft. Organizations in the healthcare sector are approached to participate in XAI research and healthcare professionals are to adopt the XAI algorithms. Therefore, considering that TU Delft to some extent depends on these relationships, this network should be maintained.</p>
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<p>Research grants</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Educational courses ▸ Use for further research
Key Resources	Key Partnerships

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Human resources, such as researchers to develop the XAI platform and its rationale ‣ Research funding for enabling the human resources ‣ XAI platform 	Healthcare professionals as input for the development
Cost structure	
University costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Researcher salaries ‣ Equipment/licenses costs ‣ Travel budgets 	

TABLE 4: TUD BUSINESS MODEL

WSC

WhitSecure is a world-renowned provider of security services through telecom operators. The company has recently invested in developing its AI capabilities to improve its attack detection and endpoint protection products. AI-based techniques are already being utilized in dynamic attack detection, identifying malicious objects, and assisting the experts at Whit Secure's Security Operations Center. WhitSecure identified for its ER a vulnerability assessment tool/library for AI systems and certification.

Organisation: WSC	Type of Organization: Industry
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ AI-based cybersecurity providers which include AI-based cybersecurity solutions developers/users (Data scientists, legal/compliance teams) and providers of solutions that protect information systems from attacks using AI solutions ‣ High-risk AI applications providers Developers/users, data scientists, CISO, legal/compliance teams, which use AI to deliver better business outcomes in high-risk applications ‣ WSC itself but also other security consulting firms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Proof of security compliance ‣ Reduces the likelihood of successful attacks against AI systems ‣ Assess and quantify the security of AI systems against well-known attacks

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Companies providing ML security assessment that can use the assessment tool to improve and ease the service provided to their customers. 	
Channels	Customer Relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ WSC plans to reach its customer segments with the following channels: ‣ Cross-sell new ML-security products to existing customers using so far only WithSecure "conventional" security products ‣ Finding new customers through an existing sales channel ‣ Partner with ML service providers for them to sell our security tools and services to their existing customers of ML services 	<p>Support</p> <p>Security consulting provided by WithSecure for expert assessment of ML systems and provision of recommendations for improvement, provision of advanced expert results</p>
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Licensing of the assessment tool for self-assessment by customer ‣ at different stages of the ML system lifecycle ‣ Licensing of the assessment tool to providers of ML security certification ‣ Consulting service fees ‣ Price per ML model/system certified: certification cost and seal provision 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Consulting services ‣ Technology-based service development ‣ Keep up-to-date with and influence ML security standards ‣ Make us WSC known as ML security experts (not only ‣ cybersecurity experts)
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Data science and security experts ‣ Training for consultants to use our tool ‣ Salesforce to push this new offering ‣ Our established security brand ‣ Software engineering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ ML service providers ‣ Authorities defining ML security standards (e.g., ISO, NIST, etc) ‣ Providers of ML security certification
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Personnel costs: consultants ‣ Tool development to preserve an up-to-date coverage of ML model and data type ‣ Customer acquisition ‣ Development of ML security brand 	

› Keep up-to-date with ML security requirements and compliance

TABLE 5: WSC BUSINESS MODEL

MI

Montimage is a research-oriented French SME that specializes in cyber-security, software development, testing services, and editor of monitoring, intrusion prevention & detection, and testing tools. SPATIAL results that Montimage is planning to exploit are:

- MMT security and performance monitoring framework with analytics based on XAI techniques for secure 5G/IoT networks
- Adaptation of XAI methods for Traffic Analysis and Classification, Anomaly Detection sale, and Root-cause Analysis

Organisation: MI Type of Organization: SME	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<p>MI's primary customer segment is Private 5G/IoT networks, which are described as IoT/5G service providers and users e.g., Industry 4.0, network operators, 5G/IoT Dev Ops engineers, 5G/IoT Security and ML Researchers/Institutions, who Deploy and operate private 5G/IoT networks, provide private 5G/IoT solutions for Industry 4.0, white/gray zones and setup 4G/5G/IoT research and testing platform.</p>	<p>MI indicated numerous value propositions and benefits that its ER mentioned above can provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Improve detection and automated management of security breaches › Time and money saving in deploying Private 4G/5G/IoT networks › Reduce the number of false positives › Quick knowledge transfer on the deployment of Private 4G/5G/IoT networks as well as Security Analysis › Ready-to-use customizable datasets for testing ML models/ applications › Security monitoring and management <p>As an additional explanation of benefits, MI pointed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Sovereign and open solutions (e.g., no back doors) › 100% in-house solution: turnkey or customized, maintenance assured

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Highly innovative solutions based on the latest research results: ‣ Real-time automated protection ‣ Technologies: DPI, CEP, AI/ML, SIEM, behavioral analysis, CTI ‣ Prevention of 0-days and APT attacks ‣ Competitive prices ‣ Software quality: verification and formal tests, reactive and dynamic team, code under certification
Channels	Customer Relationships
<p>As SME MI plans to utilize opens source, standard commercial as well as academic channels for reaching out to its customer segments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Open source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GitHub Integration in open source projects: open networking foundation ‣ Commercial Channels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media: website, LinkedIn, optimization in search engines Tenders: public and restricted Direct sales ‣ Academic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking in research collaborations, forums, conferences, Paris the regional innovation hub, ETSI standard events Publications in conferences, journals, etc. Activities in different organisations (5GPP, 6G-IA, ENISA ad-hoc WG) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ MoU (memorandum of understanding) with another stakeholder for joint offers. Co-creation-Beyond the traditional customer-vendor relationship to co-create value with customers ‣ Collaborative research ‣ Subscription services
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ An open-source model with different commercial services: ‣ Training ‣ Customizations, integrations ‣ Advanced modules, techniques, rules, algorithms, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Developing and selling own products /solutions through direct sale, ‣ distributor, licensing, online service-fee mode / Software as a service (SaaS) ‣ Consulting services ‣ Maintenance and support services

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Guarantees ‣ Subscription fees ‣ Integration in other offers with % of sales revenues and subscription services (maintenance, improvements, updated threat intelligence, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Technology services ‣ Training services ‣ Use for further research
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
Expertise, human resources Datasets for training and testing Patents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ MoU with other complementary stakeholders ‣ Collaborative research with large industry and research organizations ‣ Joint ventures (start-up creation)
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Up-to-date threat intelligence ‣ Integrations and extensions 	

TABLE 6: MI BUSINESS MODEL

MFX

Mainflux Labs is an SME company that provides end-to-end, open-source patent-free IoT platforms, edge computing solutions, and consulting services and expertise for the software and hardware layers of the internet of things technology. A SaaS platform for secure multiparty computation and privacy-preserving AI/ML is the SPATIAL result that MFX intends to exploit.

Organisation: MFX	Type of Organization: SME
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
MFX plans to target these customer segments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ IoT vendors ‣ Healthcare Hospitals/clinics running AI algorithms on sensitive user data without risk of exposing those data running AI algorithms on sensitive user data without the risk of exposing those data ‣ Finance Bank running fraud detection algorithm against sensitive data 	For all four customer segments, MFX considers that a SaaS platform for secure multiparty computation and privacy-preserving AI/ML will provide the following benefits: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ A bridge between IoT protocols and securing communication using an IoT platform ‣ Support for multi-party computations provides a backbone for the execution of complex

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<p>without risk of exposing data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public government institutions <p>Government institutions running research on sensitive data provided by private or other government institutions</p>	<p>privacy-preserving computations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data security and protection are important and in many cases confidentiality is mandatory
Channels	Customer Relationships
<p>As SME MFX also plans to utilize opens source and standard commercial channels for reaching out to its customer segments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GitHubPublic code repositories and open-source community Commercial: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online presence: website, LinkedIn, optimization in search engines Social media marketing Tenders: public and restricted Direct sales Networking Conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal assistance and support Open-source community Co-create - use customer's feedback to specify and implement improvements
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As the major revenue stream, MFX plans <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subscription fees from SaaS - Maintenance and assistance Consulting services Fundings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing and selling own products /solutions through Software as a service (SaaS) PoCs and commercial deployments in the form of SaaS and customer private clouds (Technology services) Maintenance and support services Training services Community activities
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expertise and skills/experience- human resource IP Brand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud service providers IoT manufacturers and vendors Community
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs of development (salaries) 	

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Marketing ‣ Travel and other expenses for community activities ‣ Cloud infrastructure and different service providers ‣ Other running activities (office, tools, infrastructure)

TABLE 7: MFX BUSINESS MODEL

TID

Telefónica I+D is the research group within Telefónica whose focus is technological innovation in systems, machine learning, fixed and wireless networking, online social networks, user modeling, and machine learning, distributed systems, multimedia analysis, security, and privacy. SPATIAL results that TID plans to exploit are AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency, explainability and certification.

Organisation: TID		Type of Organization: Industry	
Customer Segments		Value Propositions	
<p>As an R&D group for Telefónica, TID is planning to utilize its planned ER for Telefónica product teams who build machine learning and AI for Recommender & Personalization Services Aura (AI Agent) and Movistar TV Recommender System. The Second segment is Telefónica Tech B2B AI services, which customers include advertisement companies and mobility service providers (employing AI for optimization)</p>		<p>TID's perceived value for its segments is to free Telefonica's service providers and developers from developing federated learning models and improve the usability, and reliability of (interactive) AI systems considering that security and protection are important and in many cases confidentiality is mandatory.</p>	
Channels		Customer Relationships	
<p>Channels through Telefonica services will reach their segments are: Website, inform existing customers about the update, technology, or business events, and media publicity.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ (SaaS) service provider - subscriber relationship ‣ Open source community 	
Revenue Streams		Key Activities	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Software service subscribers charged on a regular basis depending on the type of service. For example, a targeted ad. company 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Consulting services, training services ‣ Educational courses (to help the target segments exploit the results) 	

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would pay for the queries about the customer segmentation information, possibly charged by the number of queries. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Consulting service: 1-time payment. ▸ Research funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Service quality monitoring and support ▸ Technology development ▸ Participation in technology & business event
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
Infrastructure for products (cloud, edge, etc.) and customer network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ SPATIAL partners for building technology ▸ Telefonica B2B business units that maintain existing products and clients
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Product development ▸ Publicity & marketing ▸ Customer relationship management 	

TABLE 8: TID BUSINESS MODEL

FOKUS-1

FOKUS is part of Fraunhofer institute (the leading organization of institutes of applied research and development in Europe) that has developed a number of concepts, prototypes and pre-products in the area of smart cities, Internet of Things, 3G/4G/5G, M2M-communication, AI, Next Generation Networks, Urban Data Platforms, Big Data and Open Data.

Fokus plans to exploit two SPATIAL project results, which required two business model generation canvases. The first one is for the design and application of resilient AI algorithms, explainable AI methods, and the design and realization of accountable and trustworthy based systems.

Organisation: FOKUS Type of Organization: Institute	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific Community - ▸ Research Engineers, Applied Researchers ▸ Industrial Community - Telecom providers / AI developers, System Architects ▸ Universities in Berlin - Bachelor and Master Students, Standardization Bodies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Novel applications of AI/ML and XAI ▸ Better explainability of AI algorithms to increase the utilization of AI/ML in the industry ▸ Develop an understanding of the development of Black Box AI models and their robustness

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Prototypes and demonstrators for the belongings labs as a means for › disseminating relevant technological aspects › New industrial researchers educated together with the universities in the scope of Bachelor and Master projects › New consulting and research services for German and European SMEs › New knowledge and know-how through the execution of the thesis › New researchers with industrial relevance that can execute consulting › projects for industries and SMEs › Scientific papers, which establish the team as experts in the community › Standards that increase the interoperability and transferability of AI/ML algorithms and XAI methods › Standards that increase resilience, explainability, accountability, and trustworthiness of AI/ML algorithms › Standards, methods, and tools that address the certification of AI models and AI-based systems › Standards, methods, and tools that address the implementation and deployment of explainable, accountable, and trustworthy AI models and based systems › Standards, methods, and tools that address the implementation and deployment of resilient AI/ML model
<p>Channels</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › (Scientific) Conferences › (Scientific) Journal Papers › News on FOKUS' website › Posts on social media › Acquisition/Sales › Public and private tenders › Participation in Standardisation bodies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Customized services › Consulting services › Community

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Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Consulting ▸ Services/ adaptations in industrial environments/projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Use for further research ▸ Contribute with the acquired know-how to the scientific community through workshops as well as articles in scientific journals and magazines ▸ Offer and supervise Master's theses and Bachelor's theses ▸ Standardization activities (new standards/ongoing procedures)
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific dissemination to prove knowledge/expertise/experience in the mentioned research areas ▸ Prototypes, Services, and algorithms ▸ Initiation of standardization activities or even released standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Universities & Research Institutes ▸ Industrial partners that require, development or have an interest in accountable and resilient AI-based systems ▸ Providers of telecom networks or emergency communication systems (e.g. Deutsche Telekom)
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Human Resources ▸ Administrative ▸ R&D ▸ IT Infrastructure ▸ Hardware and software costs 	

TABLE 1: FOKUS BUSINESS MODEL

FOKUS-2

The second business model generation canvas is related to a prototype of an accountable and explainable based emergency communication system that automatically detects emergencies and initiates emergency calls based on medical sensor data referred in DoA as demonstrator of an AI-based NG112 eCall system.

Organisation: FOKUS		Type of Organization: Institute	
Customer Segments		Value Propositions	

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Scientific Community - AI developers, System Architects, Research Engineers, Applied Researchers ‣ Industrial Community - Providers of emergency communication systems ‣ Telecom Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Increase emergency response time in the context of NG112 eCall systems ‣ Understanding of Emergency Detection Algorithms ‣ Lab Demonstrator ‣ Understanding of XAI in the context of emergency detection
Channels	Customer Relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ (Scientific) Conferences ‣ (Scientific) Journal Papers ‣ News on FOKUS' website ‣ Posts on social media ‣ Acquisition/Sales 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Customized services ‣ Consulting services ‣ Dedicated Persona/ Assistance ‣ Community <p>Co-creation-Beyond the traditional customer vendor relationship to co-create value with customers</p>
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Consulting ‣ Services/ adaptations in industrial environments/projects ‣ Improvement of the prototype toward a production-ready system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Use for further research
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Prototypes and Services ‣ Scientific dissemination ‣ Algorithms & Data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Universities & Research Institutes ‣ Providers of telecom networks or emergency communication systems (e.g. Deutsche Telekom)
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Human Resources ‣ Administrative ‣ R&D ‣ IT infrastructure ‣ Hardware and software costs ‣ Marketing/Sales 	

TABLE 10: FOKUS BUSINESS MODEL

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UCD

University College Dublin (UCD) is one of Europe's premier research-focused universities, renowned for its exceptional interdisciplinary research, scholarship, and innovation. The university has a notable history of successful participation in various European Union Framework Programmes, from the early days to the current Horizon 2020 program. UCD plans to exploit XAI methods for transparency and explainability and educational modules.

Organisation: UCD Type of Organization: Unviersity	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<p>Scientific Community Research engineers, Applied researchers Research community is aiming to find high quality work in the space of privacy preservation and security of networks Prospective PhD students are seeking for ideas for future research University boards are looking to deliver high quality educational modules that will make their institution /course more attractive, which will have a direct impact on employability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Delivery of AI privacy preserving platform ▸ Providing access to out-of-the-box solutions to validate and preserve privacy in networks ▸ Deliver and give open access to a platform that can be used to verify some theoretical work throughout the duration of Master/PhD ▸ The undergraduate students will gain access to educational module that is not available in other universities, which will equip them with unique set of skill and knowledge ▸ The undergraduate/master students will gain very specific set of skills that will make their profile more competetive when applying for industry or/and public jobs ▸ The PhD students will gain access to cutting-edge tools that they will be able to use in ther PhD work and use methods proposed by SPATIAL for their experimental testing ▸ The senior academic staff will gain an opportunity to use the SPATIAL platform when creating other educational modules, lecture slides or proposals for PhD/Master positions
Channels	Customer Relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific dissemination through published papers, conferences and presentations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Self-service - the research results will be published in open-access venues

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Outreach activities planned by UCD Research Department ‣ F2F networking activities, for example UCD research days ‣ UCD LinkedIn group and website including the website of computer science department. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Communities - the research progress and outcome will be shared with the research community
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Research grants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Use for further research ‣ Educational modules for undergraduate, master and PhD students ‣ Guest lectures in networking modules
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Early stage researchers in the area of AI/ML ‣ Senior researchers to take the supervisory and mentoring roles ‣ Funding is mainly sourced from projects and grants (EU and non-EU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ SPATIAL Project partners ‣ University research groups that are using AI technologies in their research/business activities, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Insight SFI - one of the largest Europe's centres undertaking research in data analytics ‣ ML labs - research center for training in machine learning ‣ CeADAR - Ireland's center for applied AI ‣ D-Real - center for research training in digitally enhanced reality
Cost structure	
<p style="text-align: center;">University costs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Researcher salaries ‣ Travel to conferences and project meetings ‣ Cost of publishing to open access journals ‣ Testing equipment required for experimental evaluation 	

TABLE 2: UCD BUSINESS MODEL

UT

University of Tartu, Estonia's leading centre of research and training, belongs to the top 1.2% of the world's best universities and member of Coimbra Group, a prestigious club of renowned research universities. University of Tartu plans to exploit Framework for verification

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and validation of software/hardware mechanisms, tools and system the solution that will provide the critical building blocks for trustworthy AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity.

Organisation: UT Type of Organization: University	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific Community in the sense of research and education for new graduates and complementary courses for curricula as well as new Ph.D. dissertations and post-doctoral training. UT has also specified SIGMOBILE (UbiComp), PerCom, and SIGCHI communities. ▸ Open-source community Apache software foundation, mostly communities that can rely on open source for non-commercial use. And as second SPATIAL API users (programmers). Providing API libraries for accessing developed microservices 	<p>UT has precisely outlined value propositions for each of its targeted segments. For the scientific community and research and education:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Deprecation of knowledge and updating courses and curricula to match demands on the market ▸ Enables the analysis of AI models within applications ▸ Provides insights about the internal decision-making of AI ▸ Graduates on the topic are experts in analyzing AI models <p>For the open-source community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Long-term support and maintainability of the open source, support for different technologies and programming languages ▸ Transfer of technologies to companies, Intuitive tools for end users ▸ A one-stop place for assessing behavior, performance, and resilience
Channels	Customer Relationships
<p>For the scientific community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Demo presentation in conference track, Organization of workshops as colocated events, submission of an article in the industrial track of the conferences <p>For the open-source community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Tools released in GitHub. Links available through personal website and ▸ research group websites. ▸ Disseminating results and insights gathered during the project on social 	<p>Research collaborations. Establishing collaborations could potentially lead to a new project, new use cases and new methods. Co-creation beyond the traditional customer-vendor relationship to co create value with customers</p>

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ media such as LinkedIn, ResearchGate 	
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ New funding opportunities to build research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Research and Development: scientific studies on XAI methods and developing XAI services as part of the SPATIAL Platform. ▸ Training doctoral (Ph.D) and Master students in line with SPATIAL research goals. ▸ Foundation for engaging in other research projects ▸ Scientific publications ▸ Technical reports, and integration into educational curricula
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Memberships in the communities (as TCP member) ▸ Scientific network for technical support (researchers that review contributions and scientific work) ▸ Scientific team to produce content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Other universities and industries with research units
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Principal investigator cost ▸ Ph.D. students ▸ Project manager ▸ Postdoctoral researchers Indirect costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Conference trips ▸ Research equipment 	

TABLE 3: UT BUSINESS MODEL

NEC

Partner NEC Europe Laboratories is a subsidiary of NEC Corporation a leader in the integration of IT and network technologies and opted for replication/cloning middleware for applications in cloud deployments as SPATIAL results for exploitation.

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Organisation: NEC		Type of Organization: Institute/Industry	
Customer Segments		Value Propositions	
NEC's is targeting in general companies and individuals using cloud infrastructure for computation, which can be divided into two basic segments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Cloud providers offering TEE-based cloud solutions ‣ Cloud customers are seeking secure cloud deployments 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Enriched offer for sensitive applications to be deployed in the cloud ‣ Increased trust in cloud deployments ‣ Enables scalable TEE applications for the cloud ‣ Provides enhances security for TEE applications deployed in the cloud 	
Channels		Customer Relationships	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Scientific conferences, fairs ‣ Meeting with BU representatives 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Personal assistance to BU representative and their deployment team ‣ Co-creation of value through specific deployments/use-cases 	
Revenue Streams		Key Activities	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Licensing ‣ Consulting 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Development ‣ Promotion among business units ‣ Design of solution tailored to the application requirements 	
Key Resources		Key Partnerships	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Improvement of current products / licensing 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ NEC Business Units 	
Cost structure			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Personne costs (development) ‣ Travel to conferences/meetings for promotion) 			

TABLE 4: NEC BUSINESS MODEL

EUR

Erasmus University Rotterdam is a globally-focused research institution that places a strong emphasis on social issues in its research and education. The Erasmus Research Centre for Media, Communication, and Culture conducts interdisciplinary research on the topics of media, communication, and culture and is committed to serving as a hub of expertise for high-quality research in these areas. The Centre includes the ERMeCC Digital Research Lab, which supports the Centre's research themes and provides resources for studying digital data and media. As the university, Erasmus is responsible for the social, educational, and ethical aspects of the SPATIAL project, is planning to further exploit its embedded socio-technical analysis.

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Organisation: EUR Type of Organization: University	
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Researchers (CS/Social Sciences) ▸ AI companies ▸ Policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Provide organizations with examples and key areas to address first ▸ Insights from the analysis may provide insight into the knowledge/skill gaps in the organizations, and a point to start education ▸ Create an understanding of areas that require more attention in practice, which can feed into policy and education
Channels	Customer Relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Academic Journals (open access): Initial plan to submit abstract to ACM CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems research design available via OSF preregistration (because of the qualitative data, EUR will not make the data openly available) LinkedIn ▸ EUR university SPATIAL website (Report D4.4 which will be publicly available) 	Consultation
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
Considering that EUR intends to offer its ER as open-source academic work, therefore no revenue is planned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Require: Research activities ▸ To provide: ▸ Insights for further research ▸ Insights for AI development ▸ Insights for EU project work on AI ▸ Policy recommendations
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Human resources: Input from project partners (in research) ▸ Financial resources: Horizon 2020 funding 	SPATIAL project partners that provide time and information and engage in research activities (interviews and site visits)
Cost structure	
Costs made for this sociotechnical analysis are personnel costs, travel costs, and administrative and practical costs for doing research (such as transcription services)	

TABLE 5: EUR BUSINESS MODEL

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AUS

Australo is a marketing company dedicated to bridging the gap between science and the market with a mission to conduct the transformation potential of cutting-edge research & innovation into its real-life applications focusing to work with communities, thought leaders, researchers, and entrepreneurs. Australo plans to benefit from all SPATIAL results and KERS.

Organisation: AUS		Type of Organization: SME	
Customer Segments		Value Propositions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific community ▸ Industries ▸ SMEs <p>In general AI developers/engineers/researchers trying to improve their dissemination, communication and community-building activities in their EU-and non-EU- funded projects and activities.</p>		<p>The improvement of the services which AUS will offer by gaining experience and exploiting the ecosystem generated by the project and our work on this topic will help its stakeholders improve their chances of being part of a new EU and- non-EU-funded project AUS encourages transparency and openness of the results and make Europe (and its researchers and scientific communities) benefit from the outcomes of the project</p>	
Channels		Customer Relationships	
Associations, DIHs, scientific forums, events, EC contacts points		Consultation, Informative, engaging	
Revenue Streams		Key Activities	
AUS's primary revenue came from European Funded projects, but also from consulting services, especially scientific communication activities.		<p>Dissemination and communication activities: Website, Press releases, videos, interviews, newsletters, blog posts. Leading WPs, and management activities. Organization of joint collaboratives activities with other EU projects; Stakeholders engagement, Communities management. Consulting services; Scientific communication and dissemination services</p>	
Key Resources		Key Partnerships	
Digital marketing and communication expertise, creativity, design knowledge, online and offline channels		<p>SPATIAL partners. Resources AUS is acquiring from partners: scientific publications, deliverables, online articles, events they have participated and have presented SPATIAL.</p>	

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Cost structure
Personnel costs, travel and conferences fees Consulting and multimedia design

TABLE 6: AUS BUSINESS MODEL

MinnaLearn -1

Partner MinnaLearn specializes in online education and learning experiences and is responsible for task 4.5 Educational module development and implementation which is also its main result for exploitation. Considering that MINI divided its customer segments into two broad categories, one consists of universities and students and the other is more B2B related. Hence MinnaLearn has filled out two business model generation canvases.

Organisation: MINI	Type of Organization: SME
Customer Segments	Value Propositions
Other universities and educational institutions Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Cost-efficiency: free module that's hosted on an external platform ‣ Online course hosted by a third-party platform makes it easy to operate ‣ Ready-made module that easily fits into a curriculum The module: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ explains the relevant concepts, technologies, and use cases from today ‣ lures more students to apply OR the student takes the course independently and decides to apply ‣ provides perspectives, exercises, and examples that give ideas to the students on research projects to pursue Introductory module to the general audience: Engage in using AI for a fair society and trustworthy products/services Technical audience: Learn the must-have skills for tomorrow's AI jobs- Dissemination and

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	<p>communication activities: Website, Press releases, videos, interviews, newsletters, blog posts. Leading WPs, and management activities. Organization of joint collaboratives activities with other EU projects; Stakeholders engagement, Communities management. Consulting services; Scientific communication and dissemination services</p>
Channels	Customer Relationships
<p>Reach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Personal networks ‣ Existing university contacts and networks ‣ Partner universities' communication channels and communities ‣ Educational publications/magazines ‣ Existing customers <p>Offering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ MinnaLearn course platform ‣ Optimized for mobile ‣ Bundling other AI courses together with SPATIAL 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Personal assistance ‣ Dedicated personal assistance
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Horizon 2020 funding ‣ Online course access sales [one-time usage fee] ‣ Online course access license fee 	<p>Production: Producing the module contents, illustrations, landing pages, and learning environment</p> <p>Maintenance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Student support ‣ FAQ's ‣ Content updates ‣ Constant coordination with the customer organizations ‣ Offering the course to existing customers as an upselling opportunity ‣ Approaching new customers interested in the field and topic ‣ Offering the module to other universities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encouraging existing students to take on the new courses
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The content provided by the SPATIAL partners The platform infrastructure and maintenance (technical infrastructure) Developers' time to maintain the learning platform Horizon 2020 funding Selling license fees to other universities Test audience (validation of the content's relevancy) 	<p>TUD, UCD, UT, EUR: content creation, offering the module to existing students, promoting the module to communities FOKUS,</p> <p>TID: Promoting the module to communities and networks</p> <p>WSC, MI: providing case examples to the module, promoting the module for employees and networks</p>
Cost structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course creation Project management [salary] Illustrations [salary] Copywriting [salary] User testing [salary] Course maintenance & updates [salary] Online learning platform operations (shared with other MinnaLearn courses) [salary, utilities] Variable costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Student support [salary] Learning group hosting [salary] 	<p>Economies of scale: Minimal variable costs (for self-study product) yield significant economies of scale from selling course licenses (Learning groups & train-the-trainer model: productized facilitator materials and digital meeting orchestration tools improve economies of scale)</p> <p>Economies of scope: A shared online learning platform among all the courses improves economies of scope (smaller cost per new course)</p> <p>--> Value-driven business: no need to minimize costs if we create a course with a wide enough audience (high gross margin due to minimal variable costs)</p>

TABLE 7: MINI BUSINESS MODEL

MinnaLearn – 2

Organisation: MinnaL		Type of Organization: SME	
Customer Segments		Value Propositions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tech consultancies Healthcare 		The module provides general know-how to both engineers and scientists as well as business	

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Robotics › Finance › Entertainment › Organizations that apply AI in general 	<p>leaders. An easy and engaging outsourced service to give the basic knowledge base to all organization workers. The module is easy to scale throughout the organization and to study at one's own pace. Tools to collaborate cross-functionally in AI projects. Improve awareness and knowledge about trustworthy AI.</p>
Channels	Customer Relationships
<p>Reach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Existing customers (sales) › Existing student base (email, online community) › Events <p>SEO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Educational publications › Reaktor community <p>Offering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › MinnaLearn course › platform › Mobile Optimization › Possible LMS integrations › Learning groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Self-service (Buying the course certificate directly from the platform) › Communities/co-creation <p>Partnerships with train the trainer model: equipping the customers to educate their employees and customers</p>
Revenue Streams	Key Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Horizon 2020 funding › Online course access sales [one-time usage fee] › Learning group service sales [one-time usage fee] › Train-the-trainer sales [recurring subscription] 	<p>Same as for the canvas 1</p>
Key Resources	Key Partnerships
<p>Financial: Horizon 2020 funding</p> <p>Physical: The platform infrastructure and maintenance (technical infrastructure)</p> <p>Human: Guiding the learning group and facilitator model around the module.</p>	<p>Same as for the canvas 1</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Test audience (validation of the content's relevancy) ‣ Project management and technical implementation Intellectual: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Insights from interviews ‣ Earlier user data ‣ MinnaLearn brand ‣ The Horizon 2020 brand ‣ The content provided by the SPATIAL partner 	
Cost structure	
Same as for the canvas 1	

TABLE 8: MINI BUSINESS MODEL

The outcomes of the Business Model Generation Workshop within the context of the SPATIAL project can be utilized in several ways. As stated in the primary objective, these outcomes can be utilized to initially test all assumptions related to partners' exploitation intentions and plans by identifying areas that may be inefficient or misaligned with their goals, priorities, possibilities, or target entities' interests.

Additionally, the outcomes of the Business Model Generation Workshop will be utilized in the second phase of exploitation activities to develop a business plan for each partner. This business plan will outline the key elements of the partner's business and outline a plan to achieve their goals with intended SPATIAL results.

4.4 BFMULO ANALYSIS AND TECHNOLOGY READINESS

On January 2023, SPATIAL partners conducted BFMULO and Technology readiness assessment of their intended exploitation results. The use of the BFMULO tool provides a means of assessing the exploitation expectations, rights, and goals of partners regarding intellectual property rights protection and their particular exploitation strategy. While, technology readiness (TRL) provides an objective and comprehensive assessment of a technology's development stage, to help identify any potential risks and challenges, and to support decision-making regarding the exploitation of SPATIAL results. The following table presents the outcomes of the analysis for each partner.

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Partner	Planned Exploitation Results (ER) (<i>description of exploitation results</i>)	BFMULO Exploitable intentions, expectations, and claims	From TRL	To TLR
TUD	ER1 - AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency and explainability; and certification	U	2	5
TUD	ER2 - User-engaged XAI interfaces	U	1	4
WSC	ER1- Methods and metrics to measure the resilience of AI systems against evasion attacks: security diagnosis	M,U,(L)	2-3	5-6
WSC	ER2 - Process to improve the resilience of AI systems against evasion attacks based on security diagnosis	U,O	2	4-5
MI	ER1- Systematic software and hardware solutions to improve the explainability, resilience and performance of AI-based security solution in 4G/5G/IoT networks	M,U,O	3	5
MI	ER2 - Effective and practical organizational adoption and adaptation guidelines to deploy private 5G/IoT networks	M,U,O	3	5
MFx	SaaS platform for secure multiparty computation and privacy-preserving AI/ML	M,U,O	3	6
TID	AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency and explainability; and certification	F, U, L, O	3	6
FOKUS	ER1 - Lab Demonstrator of an accountable and explainable AI-based NG112 emergency communication system	B, F, U, O	4	5
FOKUS	ER2 - Novel application of XAI methods in the context of AI-based NG112 eCalls	U, O	1	2
UCD	ER1- Framework to integrate accountability and privacy metrics into the existing AI algorithms	F	1	4
UCD	ER2- The re-configuration mechanism that the end-users or developers can tune to make the AI system more robust	F	1	4
UCD	ER3 - Prototype showing techniques used to improve the explainability and resiliency of the AI techniques for different cybersecurity use scenarios	F	1	5
UT	ER1 - Basic research methods to bootstrap new projects or complement on-going projects	B,F U	2	3
UT	ER2 - Research transferred to training and university courses	O	1	2
NEC	Clone-detection mechanism for Enclaves	B,M	1	3
EUR	Embedded socio-technical analysis	Scientific exploitation	n/a	n/a

TABLE 9: BFMULO AND TRL ANALYSIS

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5 MARKET RESEARCH

The previous section presented exploitation activities - consolidation of ER, Value proposition, and Business Model Generation workshops - which set the ground and direction for market research and analysis. The purpose of market research and analysis is to provide partners with more in-depth insights and information for the successful exploitation and commercialization of their intended SPATIAL results.

By providing standard market research information, such as market size, growth rate, trends, segmentation, and additional customer needs and preferences besides the one identified in exploitation activities SPATIAL partners can better understand the overall market and their target entities and customers, improve their exploitation strategies and efforts, and position better their planned ER including which channels to use, and messaging to use, which segments and particular companies/entities to prioritize.

5.1 MARKET OVERVIEW

The AI-based cybersecurity market is growing rapidly, with the global market size expected to grow by 21.4 % from 2022 to 2029, reaching nearly US\$ 68.35 Bn. at a CAGR (compound annual growth rate) of 24.2% and be valued at US\$ 91.7 Bn by 2032.

North America dominated the global artificial intelligence in the cybersecurity market in 2022, with the United States alone projected to account for over \$31.7 billion of the global market by 2032. Asia Pacific, Europe, Latin America, and the Middle East & Africa are also expected to contribute to the market, though to a lesser extent.

In the aftermath of strict government regulations and growing cyber incidents in the automotive, healthcare, government, and IT & telecommunication industries, Europe is projected strong growth prospects. For instance, the U.K. said in November 2020 that it will invest £16.5 billion (USD 21.8 billion) over four years in linked devices with AI and lots of sensors. The administration is nevertheless confident that increased defense spending will strengthen its position in Europe as it works to counter challenges from Russia and other hostile nations in cyberspace. Stakeholders anticipate increased spending by the United Kingdom, France, Germany, and Russia to identify threats and unusual activities on their networks, which has prompted cybersecurity solution providers to expand their AI portfolios.

The Asia-Pacific region is also showing strong growth in the AI-based cybersecurity market. For instance, in March 2020, The Japanese Ministry of Defense announced an investment of \$230 million to develop AI-based technology to counter cyberattacks. This type of significant investment is expected to intensify the overall market for AI in cybersecurity in the coming period. Correspondingly, China's AI-based cybersecurity market is valued at around \$6.7 billion. North America's dominant market share in the AI-based cybersecurity industry is influenced by

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various factors including the presence of established players and start-ups in the region, government initiatives to advance AI technologies, the widespread adoption of cloud-based services, and the increasing complexity and the majority of cyber attacks and threats.

Artificial intelligence in the cybersecurity market is segmented by industry verticals such as retail, government & defense, automotive & transportation, BFSI, manufacturing, infrastructure, IT & telecommunications, healthcare, aerospace, education, and energy. During the forecast period, the IT & telecommunications sector is expected to dominate the market and is among the most advanced in the adoption of AI technology[21][22][23].

Market Dynamics and Drivers

Several factors contribute to the expansion of the AI-based cybersecurity market:

The increasing number and complexity of cyber threats:

The annual cost of cybercrime is projected to exceed \$10.5 trillion globally by 2025. Comparing this to the \$3 trillion in costs in 2015, there has been a significant increase. Currently, it is believed that the annual expenses of cybercrime around the world range between \$6 and \$7 trillion, which is more than the GDP of the top three economies in the world (the US, China, and Japan). According to security specialists, there were 419 malware attacks on average every minute in Q2 2020, and Interpol estimates that over 590,000 new, distinctive malware files are developed daily. Traditional security solutions are often insufficient to protect against advanced persistent threats, which are highly sophisticated and targeted attacks that can evade detection. [24] Furthermore, AI-enabled cyberattacks leverage the power of artificial intelligence to automate and amplify the impact of malicious activities. As AI technology continues to evolve, so do the tactics and techniques used by cybercriminals. This emphasized the need for organizations to have robust AI-based cybersecurity solutions in place to protect their networks and data.

Expanding attack surfaces:

The Project background section already outlined the expansion of cyber attack surfaces which comes from several aspects. The increasing use of the internet and digitalization in both professional and personal settings, the rise of the Internet of Things and smart devices, the shift to remote work, the introduction of new devices and networks, the adoption of new technologies like 5G networks, and are some of the factors that are causing enterprise attack surfaces to grow. As these technologies become more complex and interconnected, it becomes more challenging to secure them. For the SPATIAL partners and their exploitation plans of particular interest is the IoT domain and healthcare sector. The proliferation of connected devices is creating a larger attack surface for hackers to exploit, and traditional security solutions are often not equipped to handle the volume and complexity of IoT data. In the first half of 2022, there were 57 million attacks worldwide including IoT malware, according to the

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mid-year update of the 2022 SonicWall Cyber Threat Report [25]. This attack volume is now 95% of the full-year total for 2021 and exceeds the full-year totals for 2018, 2019, or 2020.

Regarding industry-specific data, every sector evaluated revealed triple-digit attack volume increases: finance, up 151%, healthcare, up 123%, retail, up 122%, government, up 114%, and education, up 110. Ransomware topped the list of cyberattacks in the EU, closely followed by a distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, with the greatest DDoS attack ever recorded in Europe occurring in July 2022.

Healthcare cybersecurity crimes are on the rise. According to one industry report over 50 million patient records were compromised in healthcare-related data breaches last year, with a total of 905 incidents reported. This represents a 44% increase in the number of hacking incidents involving healthcare organizations. In Europe, healthcare data breaches related to cybercrime are also on the rise. The UK experienced one of the most high-profile data breaches with the WannaCry Ransomware attack in 2017, leading to an increase in cybersecurity controls. The NCSC reported mitigating 777 incidents in the past 12 months. Germany reported a doubling of healthcare-related cyber attacks in 2020, and France reported 27 breaches last year [26].

The scope and severance of cyber security problems in the IoT domain urged the EU Commission to introduce regulations and launch a new “*Cyber Resilience Act*” in September 2022. The aim of the act is to “*impose cybersecurity obligations on all products with digital elements whose intended and foreseeable use includes direct or indirect data connection to a device or network. The proposal introduces cybersecurity by design and by default principles and imposes a duty of care for the life cycle of products.*”[27]

Growing adoption of AI technology and increasing awareness of the benefits of AI-based cybersecurity. Organizations across a range of industries are adopting AI technology at an increasing rate, and cybersecurity is no exception.

In the Project Background section of this report, the advantages of AI-based cyber security solutions are many:

- Capability to analyze massive amounts of data and find trends and abnormalities that may indicate threats, enabling organizations to actively defend against attacks.
- Automatic vulnerability management and real-time threat detection.
- The automation of manual security tasks releases time and resources for other activities.
- Continuous monitoring of networks and systems for indicators of compromise, warning security personnel instantly of potential threats.

- Analyzing data from several sources, including social media, the dark web, and traditional media outlets, provides a holistic view of the danger landscape that can be utilized to drive protective decisions.

Shortage of cybersecurity professionals:

According to the World Economic Forum's 2022 report (WEF) there is still a shortage of more than 2.72 million professionals in the cybersecurity sector [28].

Government initiatives and regulations:

Governments all over the world are supporting the adoption of AI-based cybersecurity solutions through initiatives and regulations. The European Union is leading, with a number of initiatives to encourage the adoption of AI-based cybersecurity solutions, and many nations have passed laws requiring businesses to implement specific security measures.

5.2 MARKET SEGMENTATION

Taking into account the specificity of the SPATIAL project, several aspects must be considered as inputs for defining market segmentation criteria:

- The initial is SPATIAL project's context and scope regarding the particular technologies, which are AI security for mobile edge systems, 4G, 5G, networks, Internet of Things, e-Health, and decentralized cybersecurity analytics.

This also includes several other and particular technologies that include a framework for deploying privacy-preserving machine learning (Federated learning) models, Trust Execution Environments (TEE), real-time, dynamic, accountable and secure trust, identity and access management, encrypted traffic analysis and root cause analysis (RCA), automated eHealth sensor-based eCalls.

FIGURE 10: SPATIAL RESEARCH SCOPE

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- The second is the initial segmentation of target groups identified as the outcome of the first two criteria in the D6.1 SPATIAL Impact Master Plan:
 - i) AI Cybersecurity providers
 - ii) System Integrators
 - iii) Academia & RTOs

However, for the successful exploitation strategy, this initial segmentation is refined with the outcomes of the exploitation activities which consisted of consolidation for ER, and value proposition and business model generation workshops.

The following table summarizes the indication of targeted groups and segments per each SPATIAL partner.

Target segments	Interested partners
AI-based cybersecurity providers	WSC, MINI
4G/5G/IoT providers	MI, MINI
Network operators	MI, TID, FOKUS, MINI
Healthcare	TUD, FOKUS, MFX, MINI
AI-based emergency call providers	FOKUS, MINI
Mobility service providers	TID, MINI
Cloud providers offering TEE-based cloud solutions	NEC, MINI
Academia & RTOs (XAI researchers)	TUD, FOKUS, UT, EUR, AUS, MINI
Target subsegments	
High-risk AI applications providers	WSC, MINI
IoT vendors	MFX
Finance (Fintech)	MFX, MINI

Government institutions	TUD, MFX
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TABLE 19: TARGET GROUPS AND SEGMENTS PER EACH SPATIAL PARTNER

Finally, considering the nature of the AI-based cybersecurity solution market which is highly segmented, this section provides additional further segmentation, one standard, based on the range of products and solutions available to meet the needs of different end-users and industries, and in different regions of the world, and second founded on attack targets, such as users, data, applications, network, and devices.

The following is a standard market breakdown of the AI-based cybersecurity solutions market by different segments accompanied by a table:

1. End-users: The AI-based cybersecurity market serves a wide range of end-users, including small and medium-sized businesses, large enterprises, government agencies, and healthcare organizations.

2. By Deployment:

On-premises, Cloud, and hybrid

3. Geography: The AI-based cybersecurity market is global, with a presence in all major regions of the world. That being said, the market is highly concentrated in a few key regions, such as North America, Europe, and Asia Pacific.

4. Product type: The AI-based cybersecurity market includes a wide range of product types, including:

- Threat detection, prevention and response solutions
- Vulnerability management solutions
- DDoS Mitigation
- Identity and access management solutions
- Fraud detection solutions
- Email security solutions
- Network security solutions
- Endpoint security solutions
- IoT security solutions

By Product Type	Threat detection, prevention and response solutions	Airbus CyberSecurity, Nixu, Eset, BAE Systems
	Vulnerability management solutions	EclectIQ, CybelAngel, Arbor Networks
	DDoS Mitigation	Akamai, NSFOCUS, Imperva
	Identity and access management solutions	Altran Technologies, Darktrace
	Fraud detection solutions	Verafin, Feedzai, Sift Science, NS8, Arkose Labs
	Email security solutions	McAfee, Proofpoint, Mimecas, Vade Secure
	Network security solutions	Sophos, Stormshield, ESET, Nixu, B-Secure
	Endpoint security solutions	Bitdefender, Sophos, ESET, Avira
	IoT security solutions	Flexeye, Witekio, Ubirch, Cybersixgill, NetGuardians
By Deployment	On-cloud On-premise	On -premise: McAfee, Palo Alto Networks, Symantec, Barracuda Networks, Cisco Systems On cloud: Cylance, Mimecast/majority of vendors provide on-cloud based solutions
By End-user	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Aerospace, Defence and Intelligence › Banking, Financial Services and Insurance › Healthcare › Manufacturing › Retail › Public Utility › IT and Telecommunications › Other End-users Industries 	Ericsson, Nokia, Cy4Gate
By Geography	North America	Palo Alto Networks, Cylance, Check Point Software, Fortinet, Symantec, Akamai Technologies, Cisco, McAfee, CrowdStrike, VMware, Carbon Black, SentinelOne, LogRhythm, FireEye (Trellix), Okta
	Europe	Accenture, Atos, Ericsson, PwC, EY, KPMG, SAP, Nixu, Eset, BAE Systems Applied Intelligence, Airbus CyberSecurity, Bitdef, Altran

		<i>Technologies, Darktrace ender, Sophos, ESET, Avira,</i>
	Asia Pacific	<i>ZTE (China), Trend Micro (Japan)</i>
	Latin America	<i>(there is no vendors)</i>

TABLE 20: AI-BASED CYBERSECURITY SOLUTIONS MARKET BY DIFFERENT SEGMENTS

Regarding the above-mentioned SPATIAL project technology context and scope segmentation on attack targets is crucial for a successful exploitation strategy:

1. Users: Solutions that use AI to protect against threats to users, such as trojans, social engineering, and phishing attacks. Technology: machine learning algorithms to identify and block malicious traffic, and may also include features such as multi-factor authentication and user behavior analytics. Examples: identity and access management solutions, fraud detection solutions, and endpoint security solutions.

2. Data: Solutions that use AI to protect against threats to data, such as data breaches and data loss. Technology: machine learning algorithms to identify and prevent unauthorized access to data, data encryption and data loss prevention. Examples: data protection solutions and data loss prevention solutions, and data encryption.

3. Applications: Solutions that use AI to protect against threats to applications, such as malware and vulnerabilities. Technology: machine learning algorithms to identify and prevent malicious traffic and vulnerabilities, and automated patch management and vulnerability scanning. Examples: application security solutions, vulnerability management solutions and web application firewalls.

4. Network: Solutions that use AI to protect against threats to networks such as DDoS attacks, computer worms, and network vulnerabilities. Technology: machine learning algorithms to identify and prevent malicious traffic and vulnerabilities, network segmentation, firewall management, Network Access Control (NAC), and network intrusion detection systems (NIDS).

5. Devices: Solutions that use AI to protect against threats to devices, such as malware and vulnerabilities. Technology: learning algorithms to identify and prevent malicious traffic and vulnerabilities, device management and endpoint protection. Examples: endpoint security solutions, mobile device solutions, and Internet of Things security solutions.

FIGURE 11: CYBER ATTACK TARGETS

Target groups

Leveraging on SPATIAL, project scope, exploitation activities, and provided market segmentation we are in a position to provide segmentation into smaller groups with similar needs and characteristics and identify customer groups that are most likely to be interested in the SPATIAL partner's intended results for exploitation.

Another important criterion is geographic location considering that SPATIAL results primarily have to benefit the EU Academia, industry and SMEs, as well as to serve the preservation of European values.

	Target Groups	Interested partners
1	AI-based cybersecurity providers	WSC, MINI
Specialized in	Threat detection, prevention and response solutions Examples: <i>Nixu, Eset, BAE Systems Applied Intelligence, Airbus CyberSecurity</i>	
	Vulnerability management solutions Examples: <i>Securify, Sophos, EclecticIQ, CybelAngel, Arbor Networks</i>	

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	DDoS Mitigation Examples: <i>Akamai, NSFOCUS, Imperva</i>	
	Identity and access management solutions Examples <i>Altran Technologies, Darktrace</i>	
	Network security solutions Examples: <i>Sophos, Stormshield, ESET, Nixu, B-Secure</i>	
	Endpoint security solutions Examples: <i>Bitdefender, Sophos, ESET, Avira</i>	
	IoT security solutions Examples: <i>Flexeye, Witekio, Ubirch, Cybersixgill, NetGuardians</i>	
2	AI-based cybersecurity providers specialized for Network operators, Telecoms and 4G/5G providers Examples: <i>Ericsson, Nokia, Cy4Gate, Ekinops, Amartus, Baffin Bay Networks, Pradeo</i>	MI, MFX, TID, FOKUS, MINI
3	AI-based cybersecurity providers specialized for Healthcare Examples: <i>Nixu, SecuriCDS, S-RM, Wibu-Systems, ZIVVER, CybelAngel, XM Cyber</i>	TUD, FOKUS, MFX, MINI
4	AI-based eHealth sensor based emergency call providers Examples: <i>Welltok, Tunstall, HealthTap, Babylon Health</i>	FOKUS, MINI
5	Mobility service providers Examples: <i>BlaBlaCar, FlixBus, Tier, Dott, Lime, Free2Move, GoMore</i>	TID, MINI
6	Cloud providers offering TEE-based cloud solutions Examples: <i>UpCloud, Hetzner, Aruba Cloud, Exoscale</i>	NEC, MINI
7	Academia & RTOs (XAI researchers) Universities - Examples: <i>University of Helsinki, Umeå University, TU Munich HKUST, Universities of Copenhagen, Barcelona, Amsterdam, Warsaw, Milan</i> RTO - Examples: <i>VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, TNO Netherlands, Vinnova, Tecnalía Research & Innovation, CEA Tech</i>	TUD, FOKUS, UT, EUR, AUS, MINI, UCD
8	System Integrators Examples: <i>Accenture, Atos, Ericsson, PwC, EY, KPMG, SAP</i>	
	Target groups subsegments	
9	High-risk AI applications providers Examples: <i>Inbenta Technologies, DeepMind, UiPath, Facewatch</i>	WSC, MINI
10	AI-based cybersecurity providers specialized for Finance Examples: <i>Stormshield, Darktrace, Deloitte, EY, KPMG, Accenture, Atos</i>	MFX, MINI
11	AI-based cybersecurity providers specialized for Government institutions	TUD, MFX

	Examples: Airbus Defence and Space, Nixu, KPMG, Atos, Accenture, PwC	
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TABLE 10: DETAILED MARKET SEGMENTATION

This section is accompanied by an Annex document which is an extensive list of companies segmented according to this detailed segmentation and narrowing of potential entities.

5.3 COMPETITION LANDSCAPE

An important aspect of market research competition landscape overview is that it can help SPATIAL partners make informed decisions about their own exploitation strategies, identify opportunities for differentiation if any, understanding the strengths and weaknesses of their competitors, anticipating changes in the market, and responding proactively and in general position better in the market.

The competition landscape is grouped into two basic categories:

- Academia and RTO
- Commercial organizations

The following table presents all relevant organizations that can be considered competitors to the SPATIAL project and partners' exploitation strategies and objectives.

Academia and RTO	Info
EU	
ETH Zurich	A research group on responsible AI and course on Explainable AI and I
TU Munich	Explainable AI Lab, and courses on AI and Society
University of Cambridge	Course on Ethics of Artificial Intelligence and a research group on AI and society
University Paris-Saclay in France	Research center on Explainable AI
University of Edinburgh in UK	Postgraduate Course
USA (Source DARPA) [29]	
UC Berkeley	Post hoc explanations by training additional DL models
DARPA	DARPA's XAI program
Charles River Analytics	Experiment with the learned model to team an explainable, causal, probabilistic programming model
UCLA	Interpretable representations: STC-AOG , STC-PG, STC-PG+

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Oregon State	xDAPs, combination of adaptive programs, deep learning, and explainability
PARC	Three-layer architecture: learning layer (DNNs), cognitive layer (ACT-R cognitive model), explanation layer (HCI)
Carnegie Mellon University	A new scientific discipline for XRL XRL with work on new algorithms and representations
SRI	Multiple DL techniques: attentionbased mechanisms, compositional NMNs, GANs
Raytheon BBN	Semantic labeling of DNN neurons, DNN audit trail construction, Gradient-weighted class activation mapping
Texas A&M	Mimic learning framework combines DL models for prediction and shallow models for explanations Interpretable learning algorithms extract knowledge from DNNs for relevant explanations
MIT	Lincoln Laboratory
The Partnership on AI	The Partnership on AI is a non-profit group that brings together Google, Microsoft, and IBM, among other top firms and organizations working on AI. The organization maintains a working group devoted to XAI that strives to advance the field of XAI and encourage the development and use of AI in a responsible manner.
FAT ML	FAT ML is a research community that focuses on ensuring fairness, accountability, and transparency in machine learning and AI.
Commercial organisations	Info
IBM Research	IBM has developed a number of tools and methodologies for providing explainable AI, notably the IBM Watson Explainable AI (XAI) toolkit
Amazon AWS	Amazon SageMaker Clarify provides tools to help explain how machine learning (ML) models make predictions
Google Research	Google has produced a variety of tools and strategies for producing explainable AI, such as the LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) tool
Microsoft	Microsoft has been working on creating AI solutions that are trustworthy, transparent, and secure. Its Azure platform includes features such as privacy protection, ethical AI design, and secure AI model deployment.
Facebook	Meta AI
Intel	Darwin AI
OpenAI	OpenAI is a research organization that develops AI technologies that are both powerful and safe. Its focus is on developing AI systems that are transparent and trustworthy
Cloudera	Set of production machine learning capabilities for MLOps is now available in Cloudera Machine Learning (CML)

TABLE 11: COMPETITORS

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5.4 SWOT ANALYSIS

In the context of the SPATIAL project, SWOT analysis can provide valuable insights into the exploitation strategy and activities of each partner.

For researchers and engineers, a SWOT analysis can be particularly valuable as it allows them to consider their exploitation plans and objectives from a more holistic perspective, taking into account factors such as market trends and competition. Additionally, it can help identify potential roadblocks or challenges that may not be immediately apparent from a technical or research perspective. A SWOT analysis can also provide valuable insights into communication aspects of the exploitation activities. By identifying the project's strengths, more effective messaging and campaigns can be developed that highlight these strengths and differentiates the SPATIAL project from its competition. Additionally, by identifying potential threats, the team can proactively develop strategies to mitigate these threats and address potential negative perceptions of the project.

Strengths

Better performance: Transparent AI systems can improve performance by identifying and correcting biases, reducing false positives and negatives, and providing a clear understanding of the decision-making process, which can provide faster incident and threat response, cost and time savings, and more accurate decision-making.

Enhanced trust in the system: The transparency and accountability provided by the AI system's explainability enhances user understanding of its actions and limitations, leading to better decision-making and increased trust and adoption of the solution. This in turn results in higher levels of trust from customers and stakeholders, leading to potential increased budget allocation for the solutions. [30].

Reduce the risk of legal and regulatory non-compliance: By providing a clear understanding of the AI solution's decision-making process, organizations can satisfy regulatory requirements and compliance standards, such as GDPR, that mandate transparency, explainability and accountability for automated decision-making. Providing the possibility for certification of AI models and AI-based systems: Methods and tools for explainability and accountability can lead to standardization which can address the certification of AI models and AI-based systems.

Weaknesses

Trade-offs: Explainable AI system may lead to a decrease in performance or accuracy of the AI system, since this kind of system may have to make sacrifices in terms of its decision-making process. Hence, customers may prefer to use AI systems that can handle more complex tasks, even if they are not transparent or explainable.

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Lack of standardization: Lack of standardization: A lack of standardization regarding transparency and explainability in AI systems, could lead to confusion and uncertainty among users and organizations.

Opportunities

Market differentiation: The development of transparent and explainable AI systems provides organizations with an opportunity to differentiate themselves in the marketplace.

Growth in demand: Growth in demand may come from several reasons. Business continuity can come as a result of transparent and explainable AI systems in the event of an issue with the system, as organizations can quickly identify and address problems as they arise. Reputation protection if something goes wrong with the system, because they can demonstrate steps to ensure the system's transparency and explainability. Legal compliance: Some laws and regulations, such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), require companies to be able to explain how AI systems make decisions that impact individuals.

Threats

Resistance to change: Organizations may be resistant to adopting transparent and explainable AI systems due to a lack of understanding or fear of change.

Increased overhead: Additional costs for implementing and managing complex AI systems to meet additional requirements

Competition: The level of competition may intensify, as more companies enter the market with transparent and explainable AI solutions.

5.5 CONCLUSION AND STRATEGY RECOMMENDATIONS

The market for transparent, explainable and resilient artificial intelligence (AI) solutions for cybersecurity, is considered throughout the market of AI-based cybersecurity solutions. This market is experiencing significant growth and is expected to reach nearly \$68.35 billion by 2029 with a CAGR of 24.2%. North America currently dominates the market, but the Asia Pacific, Europe, Latin America, and the Middle East & Africa are also expected to contribute to the market. Europe is expected to have strong growth prospects due to the increased growing cyber incidents and government regulations such as the recently introduced Cyber Resilience Act. The IT & telecommunications sector is expected to dominate the market and is among the most advanced in the adoption of AI technology.

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The major players in the market from the EU include companies such as HCL Technologies, Airbus Defence and Space, Atos, BAE Systems Applied Intelligence, Deloitte, EY, KPMG, PwC, Accenture, and Nixu, while global leaders, mostly from the US include, IBM, Cisco, Palo Alto Networks, Fortinet, Check Point, Microsoft, AWS (Amazon Web Services), Google Cloud.

Besides standard segmentation, by geography, application, and industry verticals, special segmentation is required coming from the SPATIAL project's context and scope regarding the particular technologies, which considered market from product type and attack targets perspective as crucial for a successful exploitation strategy (end-users, applications, networks and devices and on the other hand, threat detection, prevention and response solutions, vulnerability management solutions, and IoT security solution.

The AI-based cybersecurity market is driven by several factors such as the increasing number and complexity of cyber threats, the expanding attack surfaces, and the growing adoption of AI technology and increasing awareness of its benefits in cybersecurity solutions over the traditional solutions that are often insufficient to protect against the advanced persistent and increasing number of threats, which are also becoming more and more highly sophisticated.

The main opportunities for SPATIAL partners regarding the adoption of transparent and explainable artificial intelligence (AI) solutions for cybersecurity are coming from the benefits it can provide for potential target entities including improvement of trust in AI systems, reduced risk of legal and regulatory non-compliance improved performance by identifying and correcting biases.

One of the primary challenges and adoption barriers associated with the implementation of transparent and explainable AI systems is limitations in terms of decision-making capabilities that must have to be considered as a trade-off in the implementation of such systems or features. Finally, there is also potential resistance to change in organizations caused by a lack of understanding of transparent and explainable AI systems or fear of change.

Exploitation Strategy Recommendations

“Unlike a stand-alone decision or a goal, a strategy is a coherent set of analyses, concepts, policies, arguments, and actions that respond to a high-stakes challenge.”

“If you fail to identify and analyze the obstacles, you don’t have a strategy. Instead, you have either a stretch goal, a budget, or a list of things you wish would happen.”

Richard P. Rumelt, Good Strategy/Bad Strategy: The Difference and Why It Matters

In this last section of the market research general recommendations for exploitation, and strategy is provided with the framework of Richard P. Rumelt one of the world’s most influential thinkers on strategy and management. The McKinsey Quarterly has described him as a leading

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expert in the field of strategy, a “strategy’s strategist” and a notable figure in the field [31]. He is the author of the book *“Good Strategy/Bad Strategy: The Difference and Why It Matters”* which has been reviewed positively and highly recommended by notable publications such as the Financial Times and Strategy + Business.

Richard Rumelts's strategy framework consists of coherent action backed up by an argument, an effective mixture of thought and action with a basic underlying structure he calls the kernel.

The kernel of a strategy contains three elements:

1. **A diagnosis that defines or explains the nature of the challenge.** A good diagnosis simplifies the often overwhelming complexity of reality by identifying certain aspects of the situation as critical. it should ask questions such as, What's the current situation? Why goals cannot be reached? What are the main obstacles to reaching goals?
2. **A guiding policy for dealing with the challenge.** This is an overall approach chosen to cope with or overcome the obstacles identified in the diagnosis.
3. **A set of coherent actions that are designed to carry out the guiding policy.** These are steps that are coordinated with one another to work together in accomplishing the guiding[32].

SPATIAL Strategy Kernel

1. Diagnosis of challenges:

Challenges facing SPATIAL partners for their exploitation plans and objectives are coming from several sources or aspects:

- **No clear demand from customers of AI-based cybersecurity solutions**

Customers of AI-based cybersecurity solutions are still not demanding transparent, explainable, and resilient features/modules, and are primarily interested in the advantages of AI-based solutions due to the increasing number, complexity, and severity of cyber threats. It can be assumed that this still does not create pressure for providers of AI-based security solutions to invest in transparent, explainable and resilient features/modules.

- **Insufficient demonstration of economic and productivity value propositions**

For the successful overall exploitation of the SPATIAL results strictly economic and productivity value propositions and benefits must be articulated such as cost reductions, time savings, reduced effort, simplification marketability, including the return on investment (ROI)

estimations which are significant factors that influence the decision-making of upper management in companies.

- **Trade-offs:**

The potential limitations in the capability of explainable AI systems may result in a decrease in the performance or accuracy of the AI system. This is because such systems may require sacrifices to be made in the decision-making process. As a result, customers may opt for AI systems that can handle more complex tasks, even if they lack transparency or explainability.

- **Fear of change**

Organizations may be hesitant to implement transparent and explainable AI systems due to a lack of understanding or fear of change, which can impede the adoption and integration of these systems within the organization.

- **Increased overhead:** Additional costs for implementing and managing complex AI systems to meet additional requirements

2. Recommendation for guiding policy for addressing challenges

- **Technical policy**

Increased effort and potential collaboration in addressing the significant technological challenge of minimizing limitations and balancing trade-offs of transparent and explainable AI solutions for cybersecurity.

- **Marketing and communication policies**

Refining value proposition and creation of campaign based on carefully created messaging which highlights:

- potential economic and productivity value benefits
- technical benefits such as improved detection and correction of biases
- trade-off in performance
- reputation and overall enhanced trust benefits
- reduced the risk of legal and regulatory non-compliance

as a significant resource for improving operational and production efficiency, and marketing differentiation and advantages for customers and organizations which enhance their ai-based cybersecurity solutions with transparent and explainable AI solutions features and modules.

3. A set of coherent actions that are designed to carry out the guiding policy:

- Develop visual messaging aimed to target entities' upper management that will demonstrate economic and productivity value benefits from transparent and explainable AI solutions
- Develop material that will provide and showcase evidence of technical benefits such as improved performance including correction of biases, reducing false positives and false negatives
- Create visual information material with relevant references about benefits that result from reduced risk of legal and regulatory non-compliance and enhanced trust
- Communicate visually opportunity for market differentiation, advantage, and reputation enhancement that results from all benefits
- Address directly and openly concerns about trade-offs in performance, and resistance to change with all (economic, operational, regulatory, and marketing) benefits as a counterbalance
- Include all the above communication messages for the promotion of the educational module and its content as well

SPATIAL STRATEGY KERNEL

FIGURE 12: SPATIAL STRATEGY KERNEL

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5.6 MARKET READINESS ASSESSMENT

The Market Readiness Level (MRL) is a measurement tool that assesses the readiness of a project to be brought to the market in terms of its outputs being useful, usable, and used. It measures the business-related stages that a project goes through from the start of its software development phase to becoming a market leader, utilizing its scale from Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs). In that sense, The MRL provides a clear indication of the progress of a project toward achieving its market potential, providing a scale that reflects the evolution of a project from its early stages to becoming a sustainable and resilient commercial operation. The MRL helps organizations understand the current status of their projects, and plan accordingly to ensure a successful market launch.

In the proposal phase, an initial MRL was carried out by utilizing Gartner's Magic Quadrant for Cloud AI Developer Services. It showed a rapidly maturing market where hyper-scale cloud vendors such as AWS, Google, IBM, and Microsoft are considered "leaders." SPATIAL, a project that develops methods and models for trustworthy, transparent, and resilient AI solutions for cybersecurity, is positioned in the lower-left part of the "visionaries" group, as the framework under consideration represents a change in the way AI systems operate and aligns with the European Commission's digital strategy.

However, with the consolidation of exploitation results and market research, the MRL has been updated to take into account the latest developments and advancements in the field of trustworthy, transparent, and resilient AI solutions for cybersecurity. The new assessment has focused on understanding the competition and the market offerings of similar organizations and companies. With this information, the MRL has been adjusted and updated to provide a more accurate and relevant picture of the project's market readiness level.

In terms of market readiness assessment, the SPATIAL project, as described in the information provided, is positioned still in the lower-left part of the "visionaries" group. The competition in this field is likely to be strong, with established players like IBM, Microsoft, and Google already offering AI solutions that prioritize trust and transparency. Furthermore, as outlined in the 5.3 Competition Landscape section, there are a number of academic organizations, primarily based in the United States, that are also engaged in the development of similar methods and features.

Given that these organizations have a head start in terms of development timelines compared to the SPATIAL project, and that they are all well-established and highly-regarded institutions, it is reasonable to assume that their solutions are more advanced and that they are more favorably positioned in the market.

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FIGURE 13: MARKET READINESS ASSESSMENT

With a goal of reaching TRL 5 and MRL 4, the project is likely still in the process of demonstrating its usefulness and potential value to customers and stakeholders. To capitalize on the potential market opportunity, it is recommended to implement the strategies outlined in 5.5 Conclusion and Strategy Recommendations, "B2B Elements of Value Framework", and focus on customizing communications to all relevant decision-makers of target entities in the

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second phase of exploitation activities. This will ultimately help to improve the project's market positioning and increase its visibility among relevant stakeholders.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Intermediate Exploitation plan delivered in this document outlines the activities that were conducted in the first phase of the project and provides a preliminary plan for both academic and industrial exploitation of the SPATIAL project results. It draws conclusions and drafts the next steps towards the final submission of the SPATIAL exploitation strategy to ensure that project results are fully utilized and sustainable even after the project has been completed.

One year into the project, collaboration and exchange has resulted in the completion of two significant deliverables, setting the stage for the consolidation and refinement of the individual exploitation plans outlined in the proposal phase, as well as further mapping out their pathways and categorization. The value proposition workshop and the business model canvas workshop have both played a key role in this process by helping project partners to identify the value and benefits of their exploitation results, as well as to develop a foundation for their exploitation activities.

The market research conducted as part of the project has provided important insights into the global economy, the size of the market for AI-based cybersecurity solutions, and the key barriers and challenges that need to be overcome. The results of the market research, combined with the outcomes of the workshops and a SWOT analysis, have informed the recommendations for the exploitation strategy outlined in the concluding part of this market research report.

The SWOT analysis and the diagnosis of challenges highlight the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats facing the exploitation of the SPATIAL results in the field of AI-based cybersecurity solutions. The strengths of transparent and explainable AI systems include better performance, enhanced trust, and market differentiation. However, the trade-offs, overhead cost with the fear of change are weaknesses that need to be addressed.

The opportunities include growth in demand and legal compliance, while the threats include resistance to change and competition. The diagnosis of challenges facing the exploitation of transparent and explainable AI systems reveals that there is a lack of clear demand from customers, insufficient demonstration of economic and productivity value propositions, limited capabilities, overhead costs and fear of change.

To address the challenges and maximize the exploitation of the SPATIAL results, increased efforts and collaboration are needed to minimize the limitations and balance the trade-offs of transparent and explainable AI solutions for cybersecurity. Additionally, improving the value

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proposition and creating a marketing and communication campaign that highlights the potential economic and productivity benefits, reputation benefits, and reduced risk of legal and regulatory non-compliance as well as differentiating the marketing and advantages.

In the second phase of the project, from month 19 to month 36, all partners will continue to invest a joint effort to develop the final exploitation strategy to ensure the successful exploitation of the project results.

The next steps are as follows:

- **LinkedIn Group Utilization:** The SPATIAL project will use a LinkedIn group for community building, building relationships with relevant stakeholders, encouraging engagement and feedback, raising awareness, networking, getting feedback, and sharing research results.
- **Value Propositions and Business Model Generation for use cases:** The SPATIAL project plans to develop four use cases and generate value propositions and business models for them.
- **Implementation of "B2B Elements of Value" framework:** To understand the unique needs of target entities and customers in the B2B domain and align the value proposition to each member of the buying decision team.
- **Indicative Social Return on Investment (SROI):** To assess the social impact and benefits of the project in financial terms.
- **Business Plan Creation:** The exploitation plan includes creating a business plan that covers market analysis, sales and marketing strategy, and financial background.
- **Identification of Key Decision-Makers:** The SPATIAL partners will identify key decision-makers in the buying process and tailor the values and benefits of the exploitation results to them using buyer persona Canvas.
- **Assessment of SPATIAL Project Impact:** The exploitation plan will demonstrate the relationship between the activities and the expected impact of the SPATIAL project.
- **Introduction to Go-to-Market Plan:** A go-to-market (GTM) plan is a comprehensive strategy for taking a new product or service to market. It outlines the steps and activities necessary to effectively reach and sell to target customers and to achieve specific business goals.

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Deliverables

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APPENDIX A - CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITION WORKSHOP FOR INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLANS

Appendix A of this report contains individual tables, incorporating the consolidation of exploitation results and value proposition workshops.

Organisation: TU Delft	Type of Organization: University
Exploitation Results	
AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency, explainability and certification	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Beneficiary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific exploitation ▸ Educational exploitation ▸ Knowledge transfer
Target Entity 1	
Sector	Research communities at, connected to, or impacted by research outcomes at TU Delft
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ XAI researchers looking to create new ways of explaining machine learning algorithm behaviour, either by developing new XAI methods or improving on existing ones ▸ Educators in AI fields ▸ Researchers concerned with theoretical problems surrounding XAI (ethical concerns, policy or legal concerns, anthropological/social concerns)
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Explanations generated by current explanation methods often lack in interpretability ▸ Lack of interpretability also generates obstacles in the accountability of the model's decision-making process ▸ How researcher understand accountability and explainability in AI algorithms may differ, this could lead to the development of 'incompatible' practices
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ An increased sense of accountability in decisions made by ML models ▸ Better interpretability of understanding results and understanding contributing factors/flaws in reasoning ▸ In general, improved quality of AI methods and algorithms, guidance and best practices

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Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	Develop improved XUI elements to enhance interpretability on the user end Analysis and streamlining of research framework nomenclature
Gain Creators	Conceptualize enhanced causal models for accountability Improved evaluation framework for assessing interpretability of an explanation
Exploitation Routes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Educational courses ▸ Use for further research 	

TABLE 12: TUD CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: TU Delft	Type of Organization: University
Exploitation Results	
AI methods and algorithms enabling resilient accountable metrics; privacy protection; transparency, explainability and certification	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Beneficiary	Knowledge transfer
Target Entity 2	
Sector	Healthcare sector
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Healthcare professionals use the outcome of AI algorithms in their diagnosis of certain ailments Educators in AI fields ▸ Patients or other individuals are impacted by the outcomes of AI methods and algorithms used by their healthcare provider ▸ Stakeholders that are concerned with accountability such as healthcare authorities, policy makers or other governments aim to monitor the practices of healthcare providers
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Explanations generated by current explanation methods often lack in interpretability ▸ The knowledge of healthcare professionals and patients on AI methods and algorithms may vary significantly. This lack of knowledge makes it harder to interpret results and provide patients with explanations ▸ Lack of interpretability also generates obstacles in the accountability of the model's decision-making process

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Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Improved interpretability to benefit trustworthiness from both doctors and patients ▶ An increased sense of accountability in decisions made by ML models
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Develop improved XUI elements to enhance interpretability on the user end ▶ Tailored explanation process framework based on healthcare professional requirements ▶ Define interpretability assessment targeting laypersons
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Define improved parameters for interpretability and reevaluate existing XAI methods accordingly ▶ Enhanced causal models for accountability (e.g. lessons from critical realism)
Exploitation Routes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Educational courses ▶ Use for further research 	

TABLE 24: TUD CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: WSC	Type of Organization: Industry
Exploitation Results	
A vulnerability assessment tool/library for AI systems and certification	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Owner: WSC develop metrics methods & algorithms to measure and improve the resilience of AI systems	Commercial exploitation both for improving the resilience of our AI-based systems and for creating consulting services around the AI resilience topic
Target Entity	
Sector	Primary target: AI-based cybersecurity Secondary target: High-risk AI applications
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ AI-based cybersecurity solutions developers/users (Data scientists, legal/compliance teams) > Protect information systems from attacks using AI solutions ▶ High-risk AI applications developers/users (Data scientists, CISO, Legal/compliance teams) > Use AI to deliver better business outcomes in high-risk applications
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Avoid/prevent attacks against AI systems (protect business operation and reputation) ▶ Preserve high accuracy/performance of AI systems even under attack ▶ Being compliant with security requirements and regulation around AI security

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Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ High security and performance of AI systems (better design choices) ▸ Peace of mind around the usage of AI for both WSC direct customers & its customers ▸ Knowledge/awareness about the security posture of their AI application 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Proof of security compliance ▸ Reduces the likelihood of successful attacks against AI systems ▸ Assess and quantify the security of AI systems against well-known attacks 	
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Define improved parameters for interpretability and reevaluate existing XAI methods accordingly ▸ Enhanced causal models for accountability (e.g. lessons from critical realism) 	
Exploitation Routes		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Consulting services ▸ Technology-based service development 		
Possible Competitors		Possible Market barriers
<p>Several start-ups have developed AI security /integrity services lately. They offer both technical solutions and consulting services around this topic. Robust Intelligence, TojAI, HiddenLayer and LatticeFlow are examples.</p>		<p>Lack of awareness about the security risk of AI systems. Security and resilience are not a priority in AI. AI application developers have first-hand issues to resolve before security, e.g., performance and deployment of effective ML pipelines.</p>

TABLE 25: WSC CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: MI	Type of Organization: Industry
Exploitation Results	
MMT security and performance monitoring framework with analytics based on XAI techniques for secure 5G/IoT networks Adaptation of XAI methods for Traffic Analysis and Classification, Anomaly Detection and Root-cause Analysis	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Owner of open source MMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Commercial or market-oriented exploitation for enterprises and institutions ▸ Research & Development (R&D) exploitation ▸ Educational exploitation results ▸ Joint exploitation models with partners (e.g., Cumucore)
Target Entity	
Sector	Private 5G/IoT networks
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ IoT/5G service providers and users (e.g., Industry 4.0, network operators, 5G/IoT Dev Ops engineers, 5G/IoT Security and ML Researchers/ Institutions Who > Deploy and operate private 5G/IoT networks, provide private 5G/IoT solutions for Industry 4.0, white/gray zones and setup 4G/5G/IoT research and testing platform
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Reduce vulnerability of networks to DoSS and intrusions ▸ Reduce costs (CAPEX/OPEX) in buying, deploying and operating the networks and applications ▸ Customise the solutions, e.g., add proprietary protocols, algorithms, integrate with other solutions (SIEM, SOC, Orchestrators...) ▸ Performance and scalability of AI-based behaviour analysis ▸ Understand the results of the AI solutions
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Secure 4G/5G/IoT networks ▸ Cybersecurity awareness and management, i.e., improved trust of anomaly detections and automation of security management tasks ▸ Understanding the AI-based anomaly detection and identification of root causes
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Improve detection and automated management of security breaches ▸ Time and money saving in deploying Private 4G/5G/IoT networks ▸ Reduce the number of false positives
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Quick knowledge transfer on the deployment of Private 4G/5G/IoT networks as well as Security Analysis

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Ready-to-use customizable datasets for testing ML models/ applications ▸ Security monitoring and management
Exploitation Routes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Developing and selling own products /solutions through direct sale, distributor, licensing, online service-fee mode / Software as a service (SaaS) ▸ Consulting services ▸ Maintenance and support services ▸ Technology services ▸ Training services ▸ Use for further research 	
Possible Competitors	Possible Market barriers
No equivalent open source product specifically addressing 5G/IoT network monitoring and anomaly detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Recession reduces investments in cybersecurity ▸ Lack of confidence and trust in the solutions proposed ▸ Competitors appear in the market offering similar solutions ▸ Market Readiness Level MRL6 too low micro-SME not credible enough ▸ Lack of integration with different existing commercial 5G and IoT solutions ▸ Investments needed for commercialisation (e.g., overcome the “innovation valley of death”)

TABLE 26: MI CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: MFX	Type of Organization: Industry
Exploitation Results	
SaaS platform for secure multiparty computation and privacy-preserving AI/ML	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Product creator and owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Developing and selling own products /solutions Software as a service (SaaS)
Target Entity	
Sector	IoT, healthcare, finance, public government institutions
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Bank running fraud detection algorithm against sensitive data without risk of exposing data

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Healthcare running AI algorithms on sensitive user data without risk of exposing those data ▶ Bridge between IoT protocols and securing communication using IoT platform
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Data security and protection is important and in many cases confidentiality is mandatory
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Out-of-box authentication and authorization for IoT automation ▶ A platform supporting multi-party computation
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Shortens configuration time simplifies setup, and lowers entry barriers for automation using IoT
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Support for multi-party computations provides a backbone for execution of complex privacy-preserving computations ▶ Data security and protection is important and in many cases confidentiality is mandatory
Exploitation Routes	
PoCs and commercial deployments in the form of SaaS and customer private clouds (Technology services)	
Possible Competitors	Possible Market barriers
Cosmian, Decentriq, Mythril Security	High level of novelty of the product, lack of tooling and libraries

TABLE 27: MFX CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: TID	Type of Organization: Industry
Exploitation Results	
AI methods and algorithms for privacy protection; transparency and explainability Framework for deploying privacy preserving machine learning (Federated learning) models	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Both owner (the entity participating in SPATIAL) and beneficiary (as the larger Telefónica organization which may exploit the results)	Commercial or market-oriented exploitation (possibility of new services or features)
Target Entity	
Sector	Telefónica product teams who build machine learning and AI for those recommender & personalization services

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Description	The product teams may include Aura (AI agent), Movistar TV recommender system, Telefónica Tech (B2B AI services) who develop features that explain the AI model behaviors & privacy protection or end users of recommender systems, personalization services, seek for relevant information, content, promotion	
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Concerns about un-expected behaviors of AI systems ▸ Concerns about data breaches 	
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Accountable behaviors of AI agents 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Free service providers and developers from developing federated learning models 	
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Improve usability, reliability of (interactive) AI systems ▸ Security and protection is important and in many cases confidentiality is mandatory ▸ Free service providers and developers from developing federated learning models 	
Exploitation Routes		
Consulting services, training services, educational courses (to help target audience exploit the results)		
Possible Competitors		Possible Market barriers
Internet companies leading AI research and services, and providing AI platform services (e.g., AWS, Google cloud, etc.) B2B AI companies.		Lack of awareness about the need for such a product/service.

TABLE 28: TID CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: FOKUS	Type of Organization: Institute	
Exploitation Results		
Design and application of resilient AI algorithms, Explainable AI methods, and the design and realization of accountable and trustworthy AI-based systems		
Role in Exploitation		Characterizations of Exploitation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Owner ▸ Beneficiary 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific exploitation ▸ Industrial exploitation ▸ Knowledge transfer ▸ Contributions to open-source projects and standardization
Target Entities 1		
Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific Community 	

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Industrial Community ‣ Bachelor and Master Students ‣ Standardization Bodies
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ AI developers, System Architects ‣ Research Engineers, Applied Researchers ‣ Telecom Providers ‣ Universities in Berlin / Bachelor and Master Students
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ It is currently impossible to certify AI/ML based systems ‣ AI/ML is difficult to test and verify in its operations ‣ AI/ML is not understandable after being trained and is difficult to trust ‣ Lack of highly skilled personnel in the domain of AI/ML and telecommunications ‣ AI models and applicable XAI methods are depend of the specific library and technology used ‣ Various attacks vectors for AI/ML algorithms exists that make them vulnerable to well-known attacks ‣ Black-box behaviour of AI/ML models is not understandable by human operators
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Established expertise in relevant communities ‣ Labs and support for the acquisition of industrial projects ‣ Consulting and research services in the form of industrial projects ‣ New industrial projects based on the acquired knowhow and industrial researchers ‣ Increased resilience of AI models and AI-based systems ‣ Increased explainability, accountability of AI models and AI-based systems ‣ Enable the certification of AI models and AI-based systems
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Novel applications of AI/ML and XAI ‣ Better explainability of AI algorithms to increase the utilization of AI/ML in industry ‣ Develop understanding for the development of Black Box AI models and their robustness ‣ New industrial researchers educated together with the universities in the scope of Bachelor and Master projects ‣ Standards that increase the interoperability and transferability of AI/ML algorithms and XAI methods ‣ Standards that increase the resilience of AI/ML algorithms ‣ Standards that increase the explainability, accountability, and trustworthiness of AI/ML algorithms
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‣ Scientific papers, which establish the team as experts in the community ‣ Prototypes and Demonstrators for the belongings labs as a means for disseminating relevant technological aspects ‣ New consulting and research services for German and European SMEs ‣ New knowledge and know-how through the execution of the thesis

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ New researchers with industrial relevance that can execute consulting projects for industries and SMEs ▸ Standards, methods, and tools that address the certification of AI models and AI-based systems ▸ Standards, methods, and tools that address the implementation and deployment of explainable, accountable, and trustworthy AI models and AI-based systems ▸ Standards, methods, and tools that address the implementation and deployment of resilient AI/ML models
Exploitation Routes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Use for further research ▸ Contribute with the acquired know-how to the scientific community through workshops as well as articles in scientific journals and magazines ▸ Offer and supervise Master's theses and Bachelor's theses ▸ Standardization activities (new standards/ongoing procedures) 	

TABLE 29: FOKUS CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: FOKUS	Type of Organization: Institute
Exploitation Results	
A prototype of an accountable and explainable AI-based emergency communication system that automatically detects emergencies and initiates emergency calls based on medical sensor data Demonstrator of an AI based NG112 eCall system	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Beneficiary	▸ Knowledge transfer
Target Entities 2	
Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific Community ▸ Industrial Community
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ AI developers, System Architects ▸ Research Engineers, Applied Researchers ▸ Providers of emergency communication systems ▸ Telecom Providers
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Lack of understanding of AI/ML based algorithms in the context of automated call triggering ▸ Lack of understanding for the advantages of NG112 eCalls
Gains	▸ Demonstrator to visualize the application of AI/ML and

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Demonstration of XAI technology and its benefits
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Increase emergency response time in the context of NG112 eCall systems ▸ Understanding of Emergency Detection Algorithms
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Lab Demonstrator ▸ Understanding of XAI in the context of emergency detection
Exploitation Routes	
Use for further research	

TABLE 30: CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: UCD	Type of Organization: Institute
Exploitation Results	
<p>XAI methods that can help to assure transparency and explainability</p> <p>Educational modules that can be used by the university to train future generations of researchers and students</p>	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Beneficiary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific exploitation
Target Entities	
Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific Community
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Research engineers ▸ Applied researchers ▸ Research community is aiming to find high quality work in the space of privacy preservation and security of networks ▸ Prospective PhD students are seeking for ideas for future research ▸ University boards are looking to deliver high quality educational modules that will make their institution /course more attractive, which will have a direct impact on employability
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ The lack of AI privacy preserving platform that can be easily installed on top of the existing infrastructure for example 5G testbed ▸ The lack of privacy/security platform that covers a large number of use cases and is versatile enough. Currently the out-of-the-box solutions are hard to obtain by universities ▸ Researchers are unable to verify some of their theoretical work in practical environment due to a lack of tools such as the SPATIAL platform

Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Demonstrator to visualize the application of AI/ML and › Demonstration of XAI technology and its benefits
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Delivery of AI privacy preserving platform › Providing access to out-of-the-box solutions to validate and preserve privacy in networks › Deliver and give open access to a platform that can be used to verify some theoretical work throughout the duration of Master/PhD
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › The undergraduate students will gain access to educational module that is not available in other universities, which will equip them with unique set of skill and knowledge › The undergraduate/master students will gain very specific set of skills that will make their profile more competitive when applying for industry or/and public jobs › The PhD students will gain access to cutting-edge tools that they will be able to use in ther PhD work and use methods proposed by SPATIAL for their experimental testing › The senior academic staff will gain an opportunity to use the SPATIAL platform when creating other educational modules, lecture slides or proposals for PhD/Master positions
Exploitation Routes	
Use for further research	

TABLE 31: UCD CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: UT	Type of Organization: Institute
Exploitation Results	
Framework for verification and validation of software/hardware mechanisms, tools and system solution that will provide the critical building blocks for trustworhty AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity	
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation
Partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Scientific exploitation › Contributions to open-source
Target Entities	
Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Scientific Community › Open-source community

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Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific community (IoT, Ubiquitous, Pervasive, Distributed and Mobile) ▸ Research and education: new graduates and complementary courses for curricula ▸ Research and education: new PhD dissertations and post-doctoral training University projects and Research labs
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Research: Impact may be long term instead of short term, unavailable scientific literature, lack of benchmarks and studies ▸ Software: New APIs and ready to use components from open source community, easy contributions and integration with other projects, unavailable learning material, not enough documentation
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Research: Foundational pervasive and ubiquitous methods that can build new research solutions in new projects New proof-of-concept prototypes about new innovative technologies ▸ Research and education: New skills from a concept/technology ▸ Education: Building of AI model understanding and competencies in students ▸ Industry and research institute engagement and collaboration ▸ Software: Lessons learned and experiences from developers, architects and engineers
Value Proposition	
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Research: Deprecation of knowledge ▸ Research and education: Updating courses and curricula to match demands on the market ▸ Software: It requires new skills for integrating it into a use case Long term support and maintainability of the open source, support for different technologies and programming languages
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Research: Enables the analysis of AI models within applications ▸ It provides insights about the internal decision making of AI ▸ Research and education: Graduates on the topic are experts for analyzing AI models ▸ Software: Transfer of technologies to companies, Intuitive tools for end-users ▸ AI product developers/Entities: SPATIAL platform can offer entities developing AI products a one-stop place for assessing the behavior, performance and resilience of their products
Exploitation Routes	
<p>Foundation for engaging into other research projects; scientific publications; technical reports, and integration into educational curricula</p>	

TABLE 32: UT CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

SPATIAL project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

Organisation: NEC	Type of Organization: Institute	
Exploitation Results		
Replication/cloning middleware for TEE-applications in cloud deployments		
Role in Exploitation		Characterizations of Exploitation
Owner		▸ Market-oriented exploitation / Scientific exploitation
Target Entities		
Sector	▸ Companies and individuals using cloud infrastructure for computation	
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Cloud providers offering TEE-based cloud solutions ▸ Cloud customers are seeking for secure cloud deployments 	
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scalable TEE solutions to offer to customers ▸ Lack of security mechanisms, too much trust in the cloud provider and its software stack 	
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Lack of scalability mechanisms for TEE-applications in the cloud ▸ Secure computation in scalable trusted execution environments 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Enriched offer for sensitive applications to be deployed in the cloud ▸ Increased trust in cloud deployments 	
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Enables scalable TEE-applications for the cloud ▸ Provides enhances security for TEE applications deployed in the cloud 	
Exploitation Routes		
Improvement of current products / licensing		
Possible Competitors		Possible Market barriers
Other companies designing TEE-based solutions for the cloud. We are currently not aware of other parties looking at the same problem/solution		Novelty of TEEs / Availability of TEEs

TABLE 33: NEC CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

SPATIAL project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

Organisation: EUR	Type of Organization: Institute	
Exploitation Results		
Embedded socio-technical analysis		
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation	
Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Scientific exploitation ▸ Community and policy exploitation 	
Target Entities		
Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ AI companies ▸ Researchers (CS/Social Sciences) ▸ Policy makers 	
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ AI developers ▸ AI developers community ▸ Researchers (CS/Social Sciences) ▸ Policy makers 	
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Manage/respond to demand for skilled (responsible) AI developers, or improved understanding by non-tech personnel ▸ Variations in (levels of) understanding of responsible AI and how to implement it effectively 	
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Identify gaps and areas for improvement in responsible AI development and communication on EU or national levels ▸ Provide guidance for best practices for responsible AI development on EU or national levels ▸ Improve quality of (responsible) AI development on EU or national levels (competition included) 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Provide organizations with examples and key areas to address first ▸ Insights from the analysis may provide insight into the knowledge/skill gaps in the organizations, and a point to start education 	
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Create understanding of areas that require more attention in practice, which can feed into policy and education 	
Exploitation Routes		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Training services ▸ Use for further research ▸ Policy recommendations 		

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TABLE 13: EUR CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: AUS	Type of Organization: Institute	
Exploitation Results		
As the dissemination and communication partner of the project, AUS will benefit from all results and KERs		
Role in Exploitation		Characterizations of Exploitation
Beneficiary		▸ Community exploitation
Target Entities		
Sector	▸ Scientific community, Industries, SMEs	
Description	AI developers/engineers/researchers trying to improve their dissemination, communication and communitybuilding activities in their EU-and non-EU- funded projects and activities	
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Amplify the impact generated in their research activities + improve their dissemination and communication outcomes ▸ Scientific work sometimes remains "hidden" or "opaque" to the general audience, and the communication and dissemination activities shall act as relievers by making this work approachable 	
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Our customers need a dissemination and communication partner capable of promoting their scientific activities and results ▸ We are not creating products, but we can develop new ideas about different channels to spread the project's outcomes ▸ Saves time to have the information clear and in many channels 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ The improvement of the services we will offer by gaining experience and exploiting the ecosystem generated by the project and our work on this topic will help our stakeholders improve their chances of being part of a new EU-and-non EU funded project ▸ We encourage transparency and openness of the results, and we make Europe (and its researchers and scientific communities) benefit from the outcomes of the project 	
Gain Creators	▸ The expertise gained in the project will increase our consulting services and improve our customers' dissemination and communication performances	
Exploitation Routes		
▸ Consulting services		

TABLE 35: AUS CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

SPATIAL project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

Organisation: MINI	Type of Organization: Institute	
Exploitation Results		
Highly engaging educational module that serves the needs of the academic and industry partners by bridging the gap between academic research and effective dissemination		
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation	
Implementation and lead of the educational module, further iterations and offering the module to organisations for education purposes.	Educational exploitation results used for training and/or educational purposes. The module serves as a complementary course to the existing AI-related courses (Elements of AI, Building AI, AI in Built Environment).	
Target Entity 1		
Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Other universities and educational institutions ▸ B2C overall 	
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Creation new knowledge for policymakers and businesses ▸ Do and publish research ▸ Provide relevant, topical, and up-to-date education ▸ Give students the right tools to succeed in their career 	
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ New research ideas and projects ▸ Recruit new students ▸ New research ideas and projects 	
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Lack of scalability mechanisms for TEE-applications in the cloud ▸ Secure computation in scalable trusted execution environments 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Cost-efficiency: free module that's hosted on an external platform ▸ Online course hosted by a third-party platform makes it easy to operate ▸ Ready-made module that easily fits into a curriculum 	
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ The module explains the relevant concepts, technologies, and use cases from today ▸ The module lures more students to apply OR the student takes the course independently and decides to apply ▸ The module provides perspectives, exercises, and examples that give ideas to the students on research projects to pursue 	
Exploitation Routes		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Offering the course to existing customers as an upselling opportunity › Approaching new customers interested in the field and topic › Offering the module to other universities › Encouraging existing students to take on the new course 	
Possible Competitors	Possible Market barriers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Other educational platforms: Udemy, Coursera, IBM, Maiven, MOOCs, Reforge, Modal, Datacamp, Udacity › EU-based tech companies that build their own courses and learning paths › Other open university courses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Content of the module is too general or too specific › There's not enough knowledge or appreciation for the topic › Price

TABLE 36: MINI CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Organisation: MINI	Type of Organization: Institute	
Exploitation Results		
Highly engaging educational module that serves the needs of the academic and industry partners by bridging the gap between academic research and effective dissemination		
Role in Exploitation	Characterizations of Exploitation	
Implementation and lead of the educational module, further iterations and offering the module to organisations for education purposes	Educational exploitation results used for training and/or educational purposes. The module serves as a complementary course to the existing AI-related courses (Elements of AI, Building AI, AI in Built Environment).	
Target Entity 2		
Sector	Businesses, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> › Tech consultancies › Healthcare › Robotics › Finance › Education › Entertainment 	
Description	Decision makers (in private and public organisations) Experts, like for example: product managers, team leads, software developers, data engineers, lawyers, life-long learners, students.	

	Recruit new AI talent with knowledge of the latest developments of trustworthy AI in Europe. Use AI to improve their products or to make prediction models. Make the work more cost-efficient. Improve the resilience of their AI applications.	
Pains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ The AI field and legislation develop fast and it's hard to keep up to date ▸ No company-wide understanding or know-how or education on trustworthy AI and cybersecurity ▸ The C-level doesn't understand the importance of trustworthy / sustainable AI and does not include it into strategy 	
Gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Improve the MLOps ▸ Find a common language by bridging the gap between engineers and data scientists, but also to business people ▸ Build a stronger brand image in trustworthy AI 	
Value Proposition		
Pain Relievers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ The module provides the general know-how to both engineers and scientists as well as business leaders ▸ An easy and engaging outsourced service to give the basic knowledge base to all organization workers 	
Gain Creators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ The module is easy to scale throughout the organization and to study at one's own pace ▸ Tools to collaborate cross-functionally in AI projects ▸ Improve awareness and knowledge about trustworthy AI 	
Exploitation Routes		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Offering the course to existing customers as an upselling opportunity ▸ Approaching new customers interested in the field and topic ▸ Offering the module to other universities ▸ Encouraging existing students to take on the new course 	
Possible Competitors		Possible Market barriers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Other educational platforms: Udemy, Coursera, IBM, Maiven, MOOCs, Reforge, Modal, Datacamp, Udacity ▸ EU-based tech companies that build their own courses and learning paths ▸ Other open university courses 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Content of the module is too general or too specific ▸ There's not enough knowledge or appreciation for the topic ▸ Price

TABLE 37: MINI CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS AND VALUE PROPOSITIONS

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